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**SOCIO-MORAL REFLECTION AND THE REASONS
FOR HIDING THE TRUTH**

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Abstract. *The research aims to explore the link between the results obtained with a relatively new version of a frequently used tool for evaluating moral judgment: The Socio-Moral Reflection Measure - Short Form Objective (in English: The Sociomoral Reflection Measure - Short Form Objective: SRM -SFO), whose authors are Basinger, Brugman, and Gibbs (2007), and two instruments developed by the author of this research to investigate the conditions under which people are willing to hide the truth: one in which the items have two response options (called C2), and one where they have five answer options (called C5). At the study participated 78 second-year students at a University of Arts and Design, with an average age of 20.6 years. Questionnaire C1 was administered to 33 of them, and questionnaire C5 to 45 of them. The main results indicated a negative link of the level of moral reasoning as measured with SRM-SFO with the willingness to hide the truth (measured with C5), and of the general moral value evaluation as measured with SRM-SFO with the tendency to consider hiding the truth justified (measured with C2). In comparison with the results obtained in two previous studies (Faiciuc, 2016a; Faiciuc, 2020), in the current study, the positive association of the general level of moral thinking with the relative preference for altruistic reasons of hiding the truth that focus on the preservation of the relationships with close persons, and its negative association with the egocentric reasons of hiding the truth were replicated. These obtained data can be used for the assessment of the convergent validity of the administered instruments.*

Keywords: *Moral Reasoning, Moral Judgment, Moral Value, Moral Competence, Lying.*

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND WORKING HYPOTHESES

The present research continues several previous studies (Faiciuc, 2016a, 2016b, 2020, 2021). In one of them, Faiciuc (2016b), two questionnaires were designed to explore moral judgment and moral behavior through the prism of the preference for different conditions in which the disengagement from moral behavior would be accepted. The elaborated questionnaires have closed answers, by which the respondents had to assess whether they agree or not, in

one of the variants (the questionnaire that will be called C2 in the following), or their degree of agreement, in the other variant (the questionnaire that will be called in the following C5), with a series of 31 motivations for the immoral behavior (conditions of disengagement from a moral behavior) of hiding the truth. The behavior of hiding the truth was chosen because it was considered that telling or not telling the truth is an aspect that is involved in most typical morally relevant situations and, therefore, it could be highly representative of moral/immoral behavior, in general. The idea behind the conception of the two questionnaires was presented in detail in Faiciuc (2016a) and Faiciuc (2016b). In Faiciuc (2016b), the focus was on the analysis of the answers for C2, and C5 questionnaires from the point of view of social desirability. It presents data that suggest that the indirect investigation of the hiding the truth behavior by assessing the conditions in which a person would be willing to break the corresponding moral norm may decrease the social desirability that is expected to occur when persons are asked directly if they hid the truth or not in the past. The link of the preferred self-reported motivations for hiding the truth assessed using C2, and, respectively, C5 with the moral competence and orientation assessed with Moral Competence Test (MCT, Lind, 1978, 1985) was investigated in Faiciuc (2016a), whereas, in Faiciuc (2020), the above-mentioned link was studied on another sample, a larger one, using only the C5 questionnaire. The cited works intended to find out if the self-reported preference for various reasons of hiding the truth is associated with the level of moral judgment and, respectively, with the kind of moral behavior investigated through the moral competence task of MCT, which is supposed to assess the consistency in judging the quality of the preferred types of moral arguments when they support opposing solutions for moral dilemmas, as a manifestation of a principled moral reasoning, *i.e.*, seeking the truth, and not the confirmation of a personal moral opinion.

The aims of the current study were to extend the investigation of the link between the preferred self-reported reasons for hiding the truth and moral reasoning, exploring also its relationship with moral value evaluation, and to check the results obtained in Faiciuc (2016a) and Faiciuc (2020), by using a new instrument, the Sociomoral Reflection Measure – Short Form Objective (SRM-SFO), developed by Basinger, Brugman and Gibbs (2007), which assesses the level of moral reasoning, using a different method than MCT, and, also, the self-reported importance of several basic moral values. Truth telling is among the above-mentioned basic moral values studied with SRM-SFO. So, SRM-SFO would allow also to investigate directly the link of C5, and C2, as instruments in which the focus is on the self-reported reasons for hiding the truth, with the self-reported importance attributed to truth telling, and, respectively, with the preferred moral arguments that justify its importance, providing also data regarding the convergent validity of the two instruments.

SRM-SFO develops, in an objective form, through the evaluation of predefined answers, an older instrument, also used quite frequently, but in a format that presupposes the rating of some free answers: Sociomoral Reflection Measure - Short Form (SRM-SF), elaborated by Gibbs, Basinger and Fuller (1992). This objective form of SRM-SF is more attractive from a pragmatic point of view, as it is easier to administer it to a greater diversity of subjects in terms of age and educational level, and more objectively scored than the older variant, which was based on the same traditional conceptual foundation, of a Kohlbergian type, focused on the computation of an average level of moral reasoning of the moral arguments generated by a respondent. SRM-SFO refers to socio-moral reflection from the perspectives of the importance given to different moral values in the context of various social situations, and of the preference for certain moral arguments to justify these values. The level of preference for a certain type of moral arguments reflects both a cognitive aspect, related to the ability to understand a certain moral argument and its necessity for a moral decision, but also a motivational-affective aspect, which refers to the choice from several moral arguments that a respondent is able to understand of the one that is appreciated as having a greater value, or the greatest value for that respondent.

The moral values investigated using SRM-SFO were from the domains of contract and truth, affiliation, life, property, law, and legal justice. As stated by Beerthuisen and Brugman (2016), contract and truth domain concerns the honoring of promises (made to different types of people: to a friend, stranger, or to a child), as social contracts, and speaking the truth, in general. Affiliation domain refers to the usual behavior of the children helping their parents. Life domain concerns the saving the life (and its quality) of a friend, and of a stranger. Property and law domain is about respecting the property of others, and obeying the law. Finally, legal justice domain concerns sentencing to jail of criminals by judges. SRM-SFO uses the recognition method of the moral arguments that are to be assessed by the respondents.

The moral arguments that support the importance of the moral values investigated with SRM-SFO were conceived based on Gibbs' theory of moral judgement (Gibbs, 1979), representing mainly the first four stages of Kohlberg's moral reasoning theory (Beerthuisen, Brugman, & Basinger, 2013), with which they only partially overlap (see Faiciuc, 2015). The moral arguments of the *first stage* at SRM-SFO, an immature one, are focused on the personal concrete, physical interest regarding the consequences of a moral decision. The *second stage* of the moral arguments, still an immature one, is one in which the importance of a moral value is assessed from an instrumental perspective, in the context of a reciprocal bargain. The moral arguments of the *third stage*, the first mature one, are characterized mainly by a prosocial and empathic perspective, and, to a lesser extent, by conformity to the norms of a social group (unlike the Kohlbergian model, in which the third stage is characterized mainly by the conformity to the norms of a social group). Finally, for

the *fourth stage* of the moral arguments (in which the last three Kohlbergian stages are partially merged), the fully mature one, the reflection is focused on social norms and the reasons for which they would be necessary for a particular social system, at first, or for any social system in general, ultimately.

Regardless of the initial evaluation, respondents are asked why a moral value is, at least, important, by assessing four given moral arguments, one for each of the four moral stages. For each moral argument, respondents are required to choose only one answer from three alternatives: if that moral argument is close to a moral reason they would give to support the importance of the assessed moral value, if they are not sure if that moral argument represents their way of thinking regarding the importance of that moral value, or if that argument does not resemble with the moral argument that they would use to justify the importance of the moral value in question. Finally, respondents are required to provide the reason that most resembles their own reasoning, of the reasons they designated as their own. If respondents did not perceive any of the provided reasons to be similar to their own (*i.e.*, they only selected the options ‘not sure’ and ‘no’), they were still required to choose one of the presented reasons.

Several scores can be computed based on the answers to SRM-SFO:

- the importance attributed (on a three-point Likert scale) for each of the ten assessed moral values, and their mean importance value;
- a general sociomoral reflection maturity score (which takes into account both the free answers and the forced ones, with different weights), as well as sociomoral reflection maturity scores for each of the assessed moral values, and their mean;
- the mean stage of the moral arguments designated as “close” to personal way of thinking for all moral values, as well as for each moral value;
- the stage of the moral argument selected in the forced choice requirement for each of the assessed moral values, as well as the mean stage of all the moral arguments selected based on the forced choice;
- a representativeness score for each of the four investigated moral stages, based on the number of corresponding moral arguments designated as close to the personal way of thinking;
- the percentage of the mature moral arguments (representing the last two moral stages: 3 and 4) designated as “close” to the personal way of thinking, and of the mature moral arguments (of stage 3 and 4) selected by forced choice (*i.e.*, “closest” answers);

The 31 motivations for the immoral behavior (conditions of disengagement from a moral behavior) of hiding the truth in C5 and C2 questionnaires were grouped based on theoretical considerations in five levels of maturity of the given reasons for hiding the truth, depending on the kind of consequences of the decision to hide the truth that were implied by those reasons (varying on two dimensions: concrete

vs. abstract, and personal/egocentric vs. impersonal/altruist), and on the level of self-regulation suggested by those reasons. The general idea on which the elaboration of C5 and C2 was based was similar to the idea of Palmer (2003) that offending behavior, as an immoral behavior, can be justified based on reasons that can be placed on any level of the moral reasoning. The reasons of hiding the truth that indicate rejection or ignoring the importance of the moral value of telling the truth, with a focus on the exclusive concrete personal benefit brought by the decision to hide the truth, were placed at the *lowest level* (the most immoral and immature one). For the *second level* of reasons for hiding the truth, the truth is hidden because other persons have hidden the truth, so that hiding the truth is adopted as a group norm or by virtue of reciprocity. At the *third level*, the corresponding reasons for hiding the truth suggest that the moral value of telling the truth was accepted and internalized, but it loses the competition with egocentric values that favor its hiding because of an immature level of self-regulation. The *fourth level* of reasons for hiding the truth is represented by motivations in which the competition with the moral value of telling the truth is won by convergent egocentric and altruist values that favor its hiding (as it is the case when one hides the truth to preserve/save the relationship with a close person, or a close group), so that hiding the truth may be only apparently altruistic. In this case, hiding the truth can serve moral purposes, but on immoral grounds, based also on the personal interest of the person who hides the truth. For the highest level, the fifth one, the reasons for transgressing the moral rule of telling the truth refer to other moral principles or altruist social values that may won the competition with the value of telling the truth in dilemmatic situations, or to those cases (for the C2 questionnaire) in which one is not willing the hide the truth, no matter the situation, because truth telling is considered the highest valued moral principle, and the respondent has a high functioning mature self-regulation. The difference between the C5 and C2 questionnaires regards not only the number of response options for each assessed reason for hiding the truth (a five-point Likert scale for C5, and, respectively, yes vs. no answers for C2), but regarding also the way their items can be interpreted, even though they, with only a few exceptions, are related, in general, to the same reasons for hiding the truth. C2 questionnaire allows a more hypothetical and impersonal approach, because answering to its items involves to a higher degree only a theoretical approval or rejection of the reasons that can be invoked for hiding the truth, as a personal perspective is not imposed by the wording of its items. The items of C5 questionnaire, instead, require explicitly a personal perspective, because the respondents should answer based on their personal recollections of situations in which they hid the truth for the reason described in the assessed item, or based on their willingness in the current state of mind to approve the assessed reason for hiding the truth (in case a respondent did not have the opportunity, in the past, to meet with a situation in which that kind of reason to be justified).

For C5 and C2, a general score was computed that indicates the willingness to hide the truth or, respectively, the tendency to assess hiding the truth as justified, no matter the considered reason. Then, scores for each of the five levels of reasons for hiding the truth were computed. For C5, in order to assess the relative importance of the reasons for hiding the truth and of their five levels, and to remove some possible response biases, ipsatized scores were also computed (based on the difference between the raw scores and the mean score for all the assessed items). For reasons regarding the comparison with the data obtained in Faiciuc (2020), for C5, there were computed absolute and ipsatized scores for the scales that resulted from cluster analyses that were performed for C5 on the larger sample used in Faiciuc (2020): on the one hand, scales for egocentric, altruistic and mixed reasons for hiding the truth, and, on the other hand, scales for avoidance and approach reasons for hiding the truth. For C2, also for a comparison with the data presented in Faiciuc (2016a), scores for the scales including egocentric (items from the levels 1, 2, and 3) and, respectively, altruistic (items from the levels 4, and 5) reasons for hiding the truth were computed.

Due to the large number of variables assessed with the three instruments and, correlatively, of the possible hypotheses formulated in relation to the associations between them, the working hypotheses will be formulated in a general manner.

In Faiciuc (2020), several reasons were presented for which truth telling may be considered as the epitome of moral behavior or, reversely, hiding the truth as essential in shaping immoral behavior. The same theoretical underpinning from Faiciuc (2020), in its corresponding aspects, should hold also for the present research. So, if the general tendency to tell the truth, no matter the situation, has a key importance or it is representative for a general mature moral judgment and behavior, then the general scores that indicate the tendency to hide the truth for C5, and, respectively, for C2 should be negatively associated, and, respectively, the answer for item 31 of C2 positively associated with the general scores of SRM-SFO that indicate the level of moral reasoning and the importance of moral values, with the scores that indicate the level of moral reasoning of the moral arguments with which the importance of each of the investigated moral values is supported, especially for the moral values from the contract and truth domain (the first four items of SRM-SFO), with the scores for the importance of the assessed moral values, especially from the contract and truth domain, and with the scores assessing the preference for the mature stages of the moral arguments. In the above-mentioned case, the general scores of C2, of C5, and the score for item 31 of C2 should be positively associated (negatively associated, in the case of the item 31 of C2) with the scores assessing the preference for the immature stages of the moral arguments.

If the tendency to tell the truth in every situation is not representative for a general mature moral judgment, but only the tendency to tell the truth in some situations, then it would follow that only the scores for some of the reasons for

hiding the truth would have the pattern of associations described in the previous paragraph with the above-mentioned mentioned SRM-SFO scores. Those reasons for hiding the truth should be the ones designated to be of an immature kind, which are associated with a concrete and egocentric way of thinking. In this case, the reasons of hiding the truth designated to be as the most mature ones should have rather a positive association with the general scores of SRM-SFO that indicate the level of moral maturity, with the general importance of moral values, with the scores that indicate the preferred level of moral reasoning of the moral arguments with which the importance of each of the investigated moral values is supported, especially for the moral values from the contract and truth domain (the first four items of SRM-SFO), with the scores for the importance of the assessed moral values, especially from the contract and truth domain, and with the scores assessing the preference for the mature stages of the moral arguments. Those reasons should also have rather a negative association with the SRM-SFO scores assessing the preference for the immature stages of the moral arguments.

As noted above, the strongest associations in the directions mentioned in the previous paragraphs were expected to occur between the C2 and C5 scores and the computed SRM-SFO scores for the moral values from the contract and truth domain, particularly for the telling the truth moral value, because of their common semantic link with the issue of truth expression.

The associations of the computed scores of MCT with the computed scores for C2, and C5 that were supported by data in Faiciuc (2016a), and Faiciuc (2020) should be replicated in the present research when SRM-SFO is used instead of MCT as a measure for the moral judgment maturity. Because of the differences between MCT and SRM-SFO (see Faiciuc, 2015), some of the above-mentioned correspondent hypotheses that were not supported by the results obtained in Faiciuc (2016a), and Faiciuc (2020) may be supported by the data from this research.

For more exploratory reasons, a more detailed analysis was carried out, to see the relationship of the preference for particular reasons of hiding the truth with the general moral reasoning and moral evaluation indices, as well the relationship of the level of moral reasoning and evaluation linked with particular moral values assessed with SRM-SFO with the general indices of C5, or, respectively, C2.

To my knowledge, there are no previous studies investigating directly the relationship between SRM-SFO and aspects of the lying/hiding the truth behavior. A series of studies have investigated a similar link, the one between the answers at Defining Issues Test (DIT, Rest, 1979, 1986, as cited in Chung and Hsu, 2017), as a different measure of the moral judgment development, and honesty or lying in managerial or audit reporting. For example, Chung and Hsu (2017) investigated the relationship between moral development measured with DIT and honesty in managerial reporting. Their data suggest a positive and linear relationship between honest reporting and cognitive moral development (participants at higher stages of

cognitive moral development tended to submit honest reports, giving up potential monetary gains from lying). In Ponemon's (1992) study, auditors with low DIT scores tended to underreport audit time relative to auditors with high DIT scores. Halevy, Shalvi and Verschuere (2014), instead, did not find a significant correlation of the DIT N2 score with self-reported lying frequency or lying in an honesty experimental task. Bruggeman and Hart (1996) also did not find a relationship between the level of moral reasoning, measured with DIT, and cheating and lying behavior, measured with the original Circles Test of Hartshorne and May (1928, as cited by Bruggeman & Hart, 1996), on a sample of high school students who attended either a religious or a secular school. Bruggeman and Hart (1996) noted that the failure to find a relationship between DIT and cheating and lying behavior may be specific to DIT measure. An alternative explanation for the issue of not finding a relationship between moral development measures and cheating behavior that involves also lying is suggested by studies in which such behavior and its relationship with the moral reasoning level was conditioned by particular contexts. It refers to the testing conditions. For example, Leming (1978) found that students with higher levels of moral reasoning cheated less at the Circles Test (Hartshorne & May, 1928, as cited by Leming, 1978) than those with lower levels of moral reasoning, but when the testing was accompanied by a low level of supervision, or a low level of threat from the negative consequences of being caught, they were just as likely to cheat in comparison with the students with lower levels of moral reasoning. Malinowski and Smith (1985), too, presented data that suggest that a low level of moral reasoning, measured with DIT, is associated with a higher likelihood to cheat when reporting the accuracy of the performance at a rotary pursuit task, but the cited authors noted that the investigated college students that had higher levels of moral reasoning also cheated in the testing conditions in which the temptation became strong. Synthetic older mixed results regarding the link of the moral maturity measured with DIT and interviews based on Kohlbergian method with the cheating behavior (implicitly lying) are also presented, for example, by Santrock (1975), Kupfersmid and Wonderly (1980), Heyns, van Niekerk and Le Roux (1981), Renwick and Emler (1984), and Bruggeman and Hart (1996). Studies of the association of DIT and interviews based on Kohlbergian method with delinquent or antisocial behavior that involves indirectly a lying component (e.g., Bear & Richards, 1981; Campagna & Harter, 1975; Jurkovic, 1980; McColgan, Rest & Pruitt, 1983; Nelson, Smith & Dodd, 1990; Petronio, 1980; Smetana, 1990; Raaijmakers, Engels & Van Hoof, 2005) revealed inconsistent results, suggesting predominantly that the stage of moral reasoning and delinquent or antisocial behavior have at best a weak negative association. The inconsistent results may be at least partially explained by the different samples and methodologies of this kind of studies. Some exploratory data obtained by Boessenkool (2023) suggested that SRM-SFO had better convergent validity based on its negative association with antisocial behavior than DIT, as DIT-2 was not

associated significantly with antisocial behavior. Data regarding also the validity of SRM-SF were provided by Brugman and Aleva (2004) that showed that SRM-SF and social desirability did not correlate significantly.

As noted also above, SRM-SFO, or its initial version, SRM-SF, have not been investigated so far in their association with truth telling or with lying, separately, but only in their association with delinquent, externalizing, or antisocial behavior, using scales or items in which lying was one of the aspects of the above-mentioned behavior, with mixed results also (Aleixo & Norris, 2000; Barriga, Morrison, Liao & Gibbs, 2001; Beerthuisen, 2012; Beerthuisen & Brugman, 2013; Beerthuisen & Brugman, 2016; Beerthuisen, Brugman & Basinger, 2013; Boessenkool, 2023; Brugman & Aleva, 2004; Gregg, Gibbs & Basinger, 1994; Lardén, Melin, Holst & Långström, 2006; Littler, 2015; Oosterlaken, 2013; Palmer & Hollin, 1998; Shields, Funk & Bredemeier, 2018; Tarry & Emler, 2007; Wright, 2015; see for a synthesis, O'Kane, Fawcett & Blackburn, 1996; Stams, Brugman, Deković, Van Rosmalen, Van Der Laan & Gibbs, 2006; Tarry & Emler, 2007). In this case, too, moral reasoning tended to be negatively associated with problematic antisocial or delinquent behavior, at most at a moderate level. General evaluation of moral values also tended to be negatively associated with this kind of behaviors. The mixed or weak results regarding the link between moral reasoning and morally problematic social behavior were explained not only based on methodology, but also theoretically by some authors (*e.g.*, Stevenson, Hall & Innes, 2004), based on the idea that moral maturity might not protect a person from identifying with criminal persons and from transgressing moral norms, because those transgression could be rationalized regardless of the moral reasoning level.

Some studies have tried to investigate the relationship between the level of moral reasoning related to a moral domain and moral behavior in that particular domain (*e.g.*, Ashkar & Kenny; 2007; Beerthuisen, 2012; Brugman & Aleva, 2004; Gardiner, 2019; Gibbs, 2003; Gregg, Gibbs & Basinger, 1994; Langdon, Murphy, Clare & Palmer, 2010; Littler, 2015; McDermott & Langdon, 2016; Langdon, Murphy, Clare, Stevenson & Palmer, 2011; Palmer & Hollin, 1998;). The obtained data suggest that this relationship is stronger than the one between global measures of the level of moral reasoning and the global level of problematic behavior (antisocial or delinquent behavior). For example, if the moral transgression is in the property domain (*e.g.*, theft), the stage of moral reasoning in the moral domain of property was lower than in other moral domains, such as contract and truth (Palmer & Hollin, 1998). Gregg, Gibbs and Basinger (1994), Gibbs (2003), and Brugman and Aleva (2004) showed that delinquents had particularly pronounced developmental delay of the moral reasoning in the obeying the law domain. Also, Gregg et al. (1994), and Beerthuisen and Brugman (2016) attempted to find the relationship of the delinquent and antisocial behavior with the moral value evaluation in particular moral domains. Data of Gregg *et al.* (1994) suggested that delinquents and nondelinquents rate similarly values such as promise-keeping,

helping others, and saving a life as important, differing only regarding the law domain. Beerthuisen and Brugman (2016) showed that less delinquent and antisocial behaviors were associated with higher levels of moral value evaluation only for the property, law, and legal justice domains, and, in the same time, delinquent and antisocial behaviors were not associated with the moral value evaluations in the contract, truth, and affiliation moral domains. Evaluation in the life moral domain was weakly positively associated only with the antisocial behavior, but not with the delinquent behavior. Using another measure of moral beliefs regarding cheating and lying that implied the evaluation of the importance of being honest, Matsueda (1989) obtained data in a longitudinal study that indicated a possible dynamic reciprocal relationship between such an evaluation and minor deviance. His data suggest that simple beliefs about the importance of honesty may have a greater impact on deviance at earlier ages, and that the deviant acts may decrease the importance attributed to such moral beliefs.

METHOD

Participants

The questionnaires were completed by a total number of 78 participants, second-year students at a Romanian fine arts university, with an average age of 20.6 years. Questionnaire C2 was administered to a number of 33 participants (15 girls and 12 boys, and 6 who refused to note the gender), and C5 to a number of 45 participants (31 girls and 9 boys, and 5 who refused to note the gender).

Instruments

- A questionnaire with 31 items (see Faiciuc, 2016a, 2020), C5 (see Appendix 1), in which the respondents have to specify (on a five-point Likert scale, from 0: “not at all” to 5: “entirely”) to what extent the given statements represent their motivations to hide the truth, i.e. if they have hidden or would hide the truth under various given conditions.
- A questionnaire with 31 items (see Faiciuc, 2016a), C2 (see Appendix 2), in which the respondents have to specify whether the given statements represent the way they think about the acceptable reasons for hiding the truth, that is, whether they consider it is justified to hide the truth in various given conditions.
- The SRM-SFO questionnaire, developed by Basinger et al. (2007), which is based on a model of moral judgments on four levels or stages, as stated also above. Those of level 1 indicate moral immaturity, characterized by a preference for an unilateral type of moral arguments that focus on the

physical, concrete aspects of the consequences of a moral decision. Level 2 of moral immaturity is the one in which an instrumental type of moral arguments is preferred, which concerns mutual exchanges. Level 3, with which moral maturity begins, is the one in which moral arguments that presuppose prosocial and empathic thinking are preferred, and level 4, that of full moral maturity, is characterized by a preference for moral arguments that relate to thinking in terms of justifying the importance social norms and their necessity on the grounds of a particular social system or any social system. As stated also above, each of the 10 items of the instrument has three requirements. The first one is to appreciate the importance that a respondent personally assigns (on a three-point Likert scale) to respecting a moral value in the context of evoking a situation to which it is related.

- The second one is to assess to what extent four moral arguments given to justify the importance of that moral value and which correspond to the four levels of moral reasoning indicated above, which are assigned different points in the rating (1, 2, 3, or 4 points), if chosen, are close or not to the moral argumentation that the respondent would use to support the importance of that moral value. The third requirement is to appreciate which of the previously considered moral arguments is closest to how she/he would justify the importance of that moral value. The considered domains of moral values are those related to the social contract (3 items) and truth (1 item), affiliation (1 item), saving life (2 items), respect for property (1 item), and law (2 items).

Procedure

The three paper-pencil tests were administered collectively. The two questionnaires administered for each participant were completed in the same order for all participants, within the same session, without a time limit. For C2 and C5, the scores indicating the preference for the items corresponding to the five levels of moral behavior (see Appendices 1, and 2), and a total score (for C2, this score did not include item 31) that indicates the general tendency to hide the truth or to consider that it is justified, no matter the reason, were computed. Also, as noted above, based on the scales of C5 defined in Faiciuc (2020), for C5, synthetic scores were computed regarding the preference for predominantly selfish (egocentric) motivations, for the preference for predominantly altruistic motivations, and for the preference for mixed motivations, in which altruistic and selfish motivations are in competition, as well as scores for avoidance and approach reasons for hiding the truth. In the case of the C5 questionnaire, the corresponding ipsitized scores were also calculated (obtained by realizing the difference between the answer to an item and the arithmetic mean of the answers to all items), in order to decrease possible response biases and to find out the relative importance of the assessed reasons for

hiding the truth. For C2, synthetic scores for the egocentric reasons of hiding the truth, and for the altruistic reasons of hiding the truth were computed, as in Faiciuc (2016a): the sum of the preferences for the reasons of hiding the truth of level 1, 2, and 3, in the case of the synthetic score for the egocentric reasons of hiding the truth, and the sum of the preferences for the reasons of hiding the truth of level 4, and 5, in the case of the synthetic score for the altruistic reasons of hiding the truth. For the SRM-SFO instrument all the scores mentioned above were compute. The average score of the importance given to various moral values from the 10 social situations considered in the test items was calculated, being noted as *MVE score*, as named by the authors of this instrument (Moral Value Evaluation). The general sociomoral reflection maturity score was named *SRMS score* (as was named by Brugman *et al.*, 2007). SRMS was computed using the instructions from Brugman *et al.* (2007), having a range from 100 to 400 (stage 1 corresponding to the 100 score and stage 4 to the 400 score), higher scores representing a higher level of moral reasoning. A *mean stage of the "yes" responses* was computed (divided by the number of "yes" responses). Then, it was added with the *mean stage of the moral arguments selected as the closest* to the way the respondent thinks, which was weighted twice as heavy as the mean stage of the "yes" responses. This sum was divided by three. Another global score was computed, based on the computation of a SRMS score for each item of the SRM-SFO. The stage values of the "yes" "close" responses for the four moral arguments of each item of the SRM-SFO were added and divided by four, then this average value was added with the stage value of the moral argument that was selected by the respondent as the closest way of thinking. It was weighted twice as heavy as the average stage value of the answers considered to be only close to the respondent's way of thinking. The resulted sum is then divided by three, resulting a weighted average score of the stage or level of moral reasoning for each item, i.e. *the SRMS score of an item*. The partial SRMS scores for each item were then added and divided by ten, resulting the overall *mean SRMS score*. Also, a mean of the average stage value of the "yes" "close" responses for the four moral arguments of each item of the SRM-SFO was computed. Additionally, two scores were computed for the *percentage of the moral arguments of level 3 and 4 that were considered "closed"*, and, respectively, *"closest"* to the way the respondent thinks regarding the importance of the considered moral values. Finally, a score for the "yes" "close", and, respectively, "closest" responses for each of the four stages (levels) of moral arguments was computed.

RESULTS

For SRM-SFO, the Cronbach's alpha coefficient regarding the internal consistency for the items regarding the importance attributed to the moral values was .718, regrading SRMS scores for the moral arguments justifying the

importance of the ten moral values was .728, for the moral arguments selected to be the closest to the way the respondent thinks was .63, for the preference for moral arguments of stage 1 was .734, for the preference for the moral arguments of stage 2 was .725, for the preference for moral argument of stage 3 was .559, and for the preference for moral arguments of stage 4 was .604.

For C5, the Cronbach's alpha coefficient regarding the reasons for hiding the truth of level 1 was .672, for the reasons for hiding the truth of level 2 was .813, for the reasons for hiding the truth of level 3 was .811, for the reasons for hiding the truth of level 4 was .625, for the reasons for hiding the truth of level 5 was .823, for the egocentric reasons for hiding the truth was .866, for the altruistic reasons for hiding the truth was .769, for the reasons for hiding the truth that are both egocentric and altruistic was .829, for avoidance reasons for hiding the truth was .847, and for approach reasons for hiding the truth .87.

For C2, the Cronbach's alpha coefficient regarding the reasons for hiding the truth of level 1 was .617, for the reasons for hiding the truth of level 2 was .19, for the reasons for hiding the truth of level 3 was .61, for the reasons for hiding the truth of level 4 was .686, for the reasons for hiding the truth of level 5 was .807, for the egocentric scale was .805, and for the altruistic scale was .852. The very low level of internal consistency of the scale for the reasons for hiding the truth of level 2 is partially caused, in this sample, by the very low level of variability of five of the six of its items (only 3 out of 33 participants answered affirmatively at the items 12, 20, and 27, 5 out of 33 participants answered affirmatively at the item 10, and all answered negatively at the item 13). For the remaining item (11), the data obtained in Faiciuc (2016a) suggest that it might have an ambiguous meaning.

Given the small samples and the fact that some of the involved variables had a non-normal distribution, the non-parametric Spearman rank correlations were computed. The chosen threshold for statistical significance was $p = .05$, but results close to this threshold will be reported in order to understand better the meaning of the obtained results. Bonferroni correction was not used, given the predominant exploratory character of the present research, the large number of computed correlations, and the controversy around its application (*e.g.*, Cabin & Mitchell, 2000; Streiner, 2015). The number of participants for each computation varies because of the missed answers of some of the participants.

Results for the relationship between SRM-SFO and C5 questionnaire

The results for the correlations of the synthetic variables of C5 with the synthetic variables of SRM-SFO are presented in Tables 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6.

For the detailed analysis of the association of the synthetic variables of C5 with the MVE score for each item of the SRM-SFO, the following results were obtained.

When correlating (one-tailed) the moral value evaluation score for each moral value of SRM-SFO with the 11 synthetic variables of C5 (the ones occurring in the Tables 1-6), there occurred:

- a tendency for a negative correlation of the value attributed to **“keeping a promise, if you can, to a person you hardly know”** with the preference for egocentric reasons for hiding the truth of *level 1* ($\rho = -.253, p = .055, N = 41$), and of *level 2* ($\rho = -.249, p = .054, N = 43$);
- a negative correlation of the value attributed to **“telling the truth”** with the preference for egocentric reasons for hiding the truth of *level 1* ($\rho = -.226, p = .078, N = 41$), as a tendency, and of *level 2* ($\rho = -.249, p = .054, N = 43$);
- a negative correlation of the value attributed to **“saving the life of a friend (without losing his or her own life)”** with the preference for egocentric reasons for hiding the truth of *level 1* ($\rho = -.308, p = .025, N = 41$), and of *level 2* ($\rho = -.293, p = .028, N = 43$);
- a negative correlation of the value attributed to **“saving the life of a stranger (without losing his or her own life)”** with the preference for egocentric reasons for hiding the truth of *level 1* ($\rho = -.223, p = .08, N = 41$), as a tendency, and of *level 2* ($\rho = -.367, p = .008, N = 43$), and, also as a tendency, with the score of the *scale for egocentric reasons to hide the truth* ($\rho = -.242, p = .067, N = 42$); the importance attributed to the above-mentioned moral value tended very weakly to correlate positively with the preference for altruistic reasons of *level 5* ($\rho = .218, p = .088, N = 40$);
- a tendency for a negative correlation of the value attributed to **“not taking things that belong to other people”** with the preference for egocentric reasons for hiding the truth of *level 2* ($\rho = -.253, p = .051, N = 43$), and with the preference for mixed reasons reasons for hiding the truth of *level 4* ($\rho = -.211, p = .08, N = 43$);
- a positive correlation of the value attributed to **“judges sending people who break the law to jail”** with the preference for egocentric reasons for hiding the truth of *level 1* ($\rho = .288, p = .026, N = 40$), and, as a tendency, with the preference for reasons of hiding the truth of *level 3* ($\rho = .232, p = .07, N = 42$), with the score for the *scale for egocentric reasons for hiding the truth* ($\rho = .256, p = .058, N = 39$), with the score for the *scale for approach reasons for hiding the truth* ($\rho = .245, p = .067, N = 39$), and with the score for the *general tendency to hide the truth*, i.e. the mean score of C5 ($\rho = .247, p = .067, N = 38$).

When correlating (one-tailed) the moral value evaluation for each moral value of SRM-SFO with the 11 synthetic variables of C5 (the ones occurring in the tables 1–6) in the ipsatized version:

- the importance of the moral value of “**keeping promises, if one can, to friends**” (**item 1**) correlated negatively with the *relative preference for egocentric reasons for hiding the truth* ($\rho = -.267, p = .05, N = 39$), and positively with *the relative preference for altruistic ones* ($\rho = .489, p = .001, N = 39$);
- the importance of the moral value of “**keeping promises, if you can, to a person you hardly know**” (**item 2**) correlated negatively with the *relative preference for egocentric reasons for hiding the truth* ($\rho = -.269, p = .049, N = 39$), and positively with *the relative preference for altruistic ones* ($\rho = .316, p = .025, N = 39$);
- the importance of the moral value of “**parents keeping promises, if they can, to their children**” (**item 3**) correlated negatively with the relative preference for egocentric reasons for hiding the truth of *level 2* ($\rho = -.35, p = .014, N = 39$), and positively with the relative preference for the reasons for hiding the truth of *level 3* ($\rho = .435, p = .003, N = 39$), and with the *relative preference for mixed reasons of hiding the truth, that can be both egocentric and altruistic*, ($\rho = .384, p = .008, N = 39$), and tended to correlate positively with the *relative preference for avoidance reasons for hiding the truth* ($\rho = .23, p = .08, N = 39$), and negatively with the *relative preference for approach reasons for hiding the truth* ($\rho = -.23, p = .08, N = 39$);
- the importance of the moral value of “**telling the truth**” (**item 4**) correlated positively with *the relative preference for altruistic reasons for hiding the truth* ($\rho = .316, p = .025, N = 39$);
- the importance of the moral value of “**children helping their parents**” (**item 5**) correlated positively with the relative preference for the reasons for hiding the truth of *level 3* ($\rho = .376, p = .009, N = 39$), and tended to correlate negatively with the relative preference for the reasons for hiding the truth of *level 4* ($\rho = .23, p = .08, N = 39$); it tended to correlate positively with the *relative preference for mixed reasons of hiding the truth, that can be both egocentric and altruistic*, ($\rho = .221, p = .088, N = 39$), and weakly with the *relative preference for avoidance reasons of hiding the truth* ($\rho = .225, p = .084, N = 39$), and correlated negatively with the *relative preference for egocentric reasons of hiding the truth* ($\rho = -.31, p = .027, N = 39$), and, as a weak tendency, with the *relative preference for approach reasons of hiding the truth* ($\rho = -.225, p = .084, N = 39$);

Table 1

Rank Spearman correlations of C5 variables with the global scores for moral reasoning, and moral value evaluation of SRM-SFO

		SRMS	Mean of SRMS of each item of SRMS-SFO	MVE	Mean of the mean stage of "close" answers at each item of SRMS-SFO	Mean of the stage of "closest" answers at each item of SRMS-SFO	Mean of the stage of all "close" answers of SRMS-SFO
Reasons of level 1 of C5	ρ coefficient	-.429**	-.525**	-.211	-.415**	-.473**	-.261
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.007	.002	.096	.008	.002	.059
	<i>N</i>	32	28	40	33	34	37
Reasons of level 2 of C5	ρ coefficient	-.541**	-.540**	-.359*	-.216	-.591**	-.083
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.000	.001	.011	.110	.000	.308
	<i>N</i>	34	29	41	34	36	39
Reasons of level 3 of C5	ρ coefficient	-.187	-.239	-.012	-.224	-.245	-.073
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.145	.106	.471	.102	.075	.330
	<i>N</i>	34	29	41	34	36	39
Reasons of level 4 of C5	ρ coefficient	.081	.003	-.158	.156	.002	.201
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.324	.493	.162	.189	.495	.109
	<i>N</i>	34	29	41	34	36	39
Reasons of level 5 of C5	ρ coefficient	-.042	-.093	.065	-.184	-.104	-.087
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.406	.316	.347	.149	.277	.299
	<i>N</i>	34	29	39	34	35	39
Egocentric reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	-.433**	-.447**	-.212	-.274	-.495**	-.153
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.007	.009	.097	.062	.001	.183
	<i>N</i>	32	28	39	33	34	37
Altruistic reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	-.073	-.122	.066	-.223	-.130	-.119
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.341	.264	.343	.102	.228	.235
	<i>N</i>	34	29	40	34	35	39
Mixed reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	-.126	-.217	-.044	-.172	-.194	-.011
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.238	.130	.393	.166	.129	.474
	<i>N</i>	34	29	41	34	36	39
Avoidance reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	-.060	-.154	.056	-.185	-.130	-.011
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.368	.213	.365	.147	.225	.474
	<i>N</i>	34	29	40	34	36	39
Approach reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	-.390*	-.415*	-.124	-.328*	-.437**	-.210
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.014	.014	.225	.031	.005	.106
	<i>N</i>	32	28	39	33	33	37
Mean of C5 (tendency to hide the truth)	ρ coefficient	-.256	-.318*	-.001	-.261	-.306*	-.129
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.079	.049	.497	.071	.042	.223
	<i>N</i>	32	28	38	33	33	37

* $p < .05$ ** $p < .01$

Table 2

Rank Spearman correlations of C5 *ipsatized* variables with the global scores for moral reasoning, and moral value evaluation of SRM-SFO

		SRMS	Mean of SRMS of each item of SRMS-SFO	MVE	Mean of the mean stage of "close" answers at each item of SRMS-SFO	Mean of the stage of "closest" answers at each item of SRMS-SFO	Mean of the stage of all "close" answers of SRMS-SFO
Reasons of level 1 of C5	ρ coefficient	-.089	-.192	-.168	-.212	-.082	-.203
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.314	.164	.156	.118	.325	.114
	N	32	28	38	33	33	37
Reasons of level 2 of C5	ρ coefficient	-.476**	-.432*	-.399**	-.116	-.470**	-.082
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.003	.011	.007	.260	.003	.314
	N	32	28	38	33	33	37
Reasons of level 3 of C5	ρ coefficient	-.012	-.034	.285*	-.073	.012	-.025
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.473	.431	.042	.343	.474	.442
	N	32	28	38	33	33	37
Reasons of level 4 of C5	ρ coefficient	.398*	.348*	-.184	.429**	.361*	.331*
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.012	.035	.134	.006	.020	.023
	N	32	28	38	33	33	37
Reasons of level 5 of C5	ρ coefficient	.026	.002	.146	-.132	-.008	-.101
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.444	.497	.191	.231	.483	.276
	N	32	28	38	33	33	37
Egocentric reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	-.310*	-.284	-.419**	-.137	-.339*	-.040
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.042	.072	.004	.224	.027	.407
	N	32	28	38	33	33	37
Altruistic reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	.378*	.407*	.392**	.075	.412**	-.089
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.017	.016	.007	.339	.009	.300
	N	32	28	38	33	33	37
Mixed reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	.055	-.027	.157	.041	.046	.107
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.383	.447	.173	.410	.400	.264
	N	32	28	38	33	33	37
Avoidance reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	.295	.185	.207	.193	.265	.257
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.051	.173	.106	.141	.068	.062
	N	32	28	38	33	33	37
Approach reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	-.295	-.185	-.207	-.193	-.265	-.257
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.051	.173	.106	.141	.068	.062
	N	32	28	38	33	33	37

* $p < .05$ ** $p < .01$

- the importance of the moral value of “**saving the life of a friend (without losing his or her own life)**” (item 6) correlated negatively with the relative preference for egocentric reasons for hiding the truth of level 1 ($\rho = -.358$,

$p = .013$, $N = 39$), and with the relative preference for the reasons for hiding the truth of level 2 ($\rho = -.282$, $p = .041$, $N = 39$); it correlated positively with the *relative preference for altruistic reasons of hiding the truth* ($\rho = .271$, $p = .048$, $N = 39$), and tended to correlate positively with the *relative preference for avoidance reasons for hiding the truth* ($\rho = .231$, $p = .078$, $N = 39$), and negatively with the *relative preference for egocentric reasons for hiding the truth* ($\rho = -.265$, $p = .051$, $N = 39$), and with the *relative preference for approach reasons for hiding the truth* ($\rho = -.231$, $p = .078$, $N = 39$);

- the importance of the moral value of “**saving the life of a stranger (without losing his or her own life)**” (item 7) correlated negatively with the relative preference for egocentric reasons for hiding the truth of level 2 ($\rho = -.496$, $p = .001$, $N = 39$), and tended to correlate positively with the relative preference for the altruistic reasons for hiding the truth of level 5 ($\rho = .25$, $p = .062$, $N = 39$); it correlated positively with the *relative preference for altruistic reasons of hiding the truth* ($\rho = .472$, $p = .001$, $N = 39$), and with the *relative preference for avoidance reasons of hiding the truth* ($\rho = .323$, $p = .023$, $N = 39$), and negatively with the *relative preference for egocentric reasons of hiding the truth* ($\rho = -.516$, $p < .001$, $N = 39$), and with the *relative preference for approach reasons of hiding the truth* ($\rho = -.323$, $p = .023$, $N = 39$);

Table 3

Rank Spearman correlations of C5 variables with the scores for the preferred stages of moral reasoning of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO

		Stage 1 closest	Stage 2 closest	Stage 3 closest	Stage 4 closest	Percentage of stage 3 and 4 of “closest” answers
Reasons of level 1 of C5	ρ coefficient	.245	.438**	-.065	-.437**	-.522**
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.085	.005	.360	.006	.001
	N	33	33	33	33	33
Reasons of level 2 of C5	ρ coefficient	.262	.457**	.314*	-.602**	-.578**
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.064	.003	.033	.000	.000
	N	35	35	35	35	35
Reasons of level 3 of C5	ρ coefficient	-.001	.238	.114	-.300*	-.210
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.498	.084	.258	.040	.113
	N	35	35	35	35	35
Reasons of level 4 of C5	ρ coefficient	-.213	.131	.255	-.083	-.032
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.110	.226	.070	.318	.427
	N	35	35	35	35	35
Reasons of level 5 of C5	ρ coefficient	-.041	.158	.002	-.095	-.150
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.409	.185	.496	.297	.199
	N	34	34	34	34	34

		Stage 1 closest	Stage 2 closest	Stage 3 closest	Stage 4 closest	Percentage of stage 3 and 4 of "closest" answers
Egocentric reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	.222	.426**	.199	-.497**	-.498**
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.107	.007	.134	.002	.002
	<i>N</i>	33	33	33	33	33
Altruistic reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	-.087	.232	.048	-.154	-.188
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.312	.094	.394	.192	.143
	<i>N</i>	34	34	34	34	34
Mixed reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	-.067	.222	.142	-.258	-.171
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.352	.100	.208	.067	.163
	<i>N</i>	35	35	35	35	35
Avoidance reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	-.120	.259	.059	-.180	-.176
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.247	.066	.369	.151	.156
	<i>N</i>	35	35	35	35	35
Approach reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	.188	.338*	.173	-.434**	-.424**
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.151	.029	.173	.007	.008
	<i>N</i>	32	32	32	32	32
Mean of C5 (tendency to hide the truth)	ρ coefficient	.065	.281	.120	-.315*	-.306*
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.362	.060	.256	.040	.044
	<i>N</i>	32	32	32	32	32

* $p < .05$ ** $p < .01$

Table 4

Rank Spearman correlations of C5 variables with the scores for the preferred stages of moral reasoning of the "close" answers at SRM-SFO

		Stage 1 close	Stage 2 close	Stage 3 close	Stage 4 close	Percentage of stage 3 and 4 of "close" answers
Reasons of level 1 of C5	ρ coefficient	.078	.131	.026	-.333*	-.198
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.323	.221	.438	.022	.121
	<i>N</i>	37	37	37	37	37
Reasons of level 2 of C5	ρ coefficient	-.075	.009	.020	-.396**	-.182
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.325	.479	.452	.006	.134
	<i>N</i>	39	39	39	39	39
Reasons of level 3 of C5	ρ coefficient	.039	.156	.175	-.128	.060
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.408	.171	.144	.219	.358
	<i>N</i>	39	39	39	39	39
Reasons of level 4 of C5	ρ coefficient	-.197	.039	.113	-.054	.074
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.114	.406	.246	.373	.327
	<i>N</i>	39	39	39	39	39

		Stage 1 close	Stage 2 close	Stage 3 close	Stage 4 close	Percentage of stage 3 and 4 of “close” answers
Reasons of level 5 of C5	ρ coefficient	.034	.032	-.023	-.109	-.086
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.418	.424	.444	.254	.301
	<i>N</i>	39	39	39	39	39
Egocentric reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	-.027	.033	-.023	-.346*	-.223
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.436	.423	.445	.018	.092
	<i>N</i>	37	37	37	37	37
Altruistic reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	.077	.107	.073	-.085	-.003
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.321	.258	.330	.303	.493
	<i>N</i>	39	39	39	39	39
Mixed reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	-.012	.153	.161	-.112	.063
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.472	.176	.164	.248	.351
	<i>N</i>	39	39	39	39	39
Avoidance reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	-.028	.121	.092	-.120	.012
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.433	.231	.288	.233	.472
	<i>N</i>	39	39	39	39	39
Approach reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	.100	.107	.075	-.235	-.089
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.278	.264	.330	.081	.300
	<i>N</i>	37	37	37	37	37
Mean of C5 (tendency to hide the truth)	ρ coefficient	.051	.121	.109	-.183	-.029
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.383	.239	.260	.139	.432
	<i>N</i>	37	37	37	37	37

* $p < .05$ ** $p < .01$

- the importance of the moral value of “**not taking things that belong to other people**” (item 8) correlated positively with the *relative preference for altruistic reasons of hiding the truth* ($\rho = .407$, $p = .005$, $N = 39$), and tended to correlated negatively with relative preference for the reasons for hiding the truth of level 4 ($\rho = -.257$, $p = .057$, $N = 39$);
- the importance of the moral value of “**judges sending people who break the law to jail**” (item 10) tended to correlate positively with the relative preference for egocentric reasons for hiding the truth of level 1 ($\rho = .246$, $p = .068$, $N = 38$), and negatively with the *relative preference for altruistic reasons of hiding the truth* ($\rho = -.264$, $p = .055$, $N = 38$).

Tables 7–12 present the correlations between C5 variables and the three types of scores that indicate the level of moral reasoning for each item of SRM-SFO.

Table 5

Rank Spearman correlations of C5 *ipsatized* variables with the scores for the preferred stages of moral reasoning of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO

		Stage 1 closest	Stage 2 closest	Stage 3 closest	Stage 4 closest	Percentage of stage 3 and 4 of “closest” answers
Reasons of level 1 of C5	ρ coefficient	.225	.086	-.359*	.009	-.187
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.108	.320	.022	.481	.153
	N	32	32	32	32	32
Reasons of level 2 of C5	ρ coefficient	.398*	.284	.206	-.418**	-.482**
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.012	.058	.129	.009	.003
	N	32	32	32	32	32
Reasons of level 3 of C5	ρ coefficient	-.131	-.018	.040	-.057	.125
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.237	.462	.414	.379	.248
	N	32	32	32	32	32
Reasons of level 4 of C5	ρ coefficient	-.394*	-.186	.290	.226	.352*
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.013	.154	.054	.107	.024
	N	32	32	32	32	32
Reasons of level 5 of C5	ρ coefficient	-.082	.066	-.037	.024	-.039
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.327	.360	.420	.448	.417
	N	32	32	32	32	32
Egocentric reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	.362*	.217	.082	-.308*	-.382*
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.021	.116	.328	.043	.015
	N	32	32	32	32	32
Altruistic reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	-.318*	-.215	-.164	.410**	.349*
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.038	.119	.184	.010	.025
	N	32	32	32	32	32
Mixed reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	-.152	-.060	.100	-.031	.163
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.203	.371	.293	.434	.186
	N	32	32	32	32	32
Avoidance reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	-.346*	-.052	-.033	.180	.259
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.026	.389	.429	.162	.076
	N	32	32	32	32	32
Approach reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	.346*	.052	.033	-.180	-.259
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.026	.389	.429	.162	.076
	N	32	32	32	32	32

* $p < .05$ ** $p < .01$

Results for the relationship between SRM-SFO and C2 questionnaire

The computed scores for the C2 questionnaire correlated (one-tailed) or tended to correlate mainly with the MVE score (see Table 13) of the global scores of SRM-SFO. The only C2 score that correlated statistically significantly with SRM-SFO global scores that indicate the level of moral reasoning was the one for the reasons of hiding the truth of level 2 (see Table 14). The reasons of hiding the

truth of level 3, and the score for the egocentric reasons for hiding the truth tended to correlate negatively with the mean of the mean stage of “close” answers at each item of SRMS-SFO ($\rho = -.34$, $p = .056$, $N = 23$, and, respectively, $\rho = -.347$, $p = .057$, $N = 22$). Rank Spearman correlations of C2 variables with the scores for the preferred stages of moral reasoning of the “close” and “closest” answers at SRM-SFO are presented in Table 15.

The rank correlations between the C2 scores and the scores for each item of SRM-SFO are included in the Tables 16, 17, 18, and 19.

Table 6

Rank Spearman correlations of C5 *ipsatized* variables with the scores for the preferred stages of moral reasoning of the “close” answers at SRM-SFO

		Stage 1 close	Stage 2 close	Stage 3 close	Stage 4 close	Percentage of stage 3 and 4 of “close” answers
Reasons of level 1 of C5	ρ coefficient	.071	-.032	-.257	-.261	-.353*
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.339	.424	.063	.060	.016
	N	37	37	37	37	37
Reasons of level 2 of C5	ρ coefficient	-.071	-.051	-.245	-.271	-.287*
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.339	.383	.072	.052	.043
	N	37	37	37	37	37
Reasons of level 3 of C5	ρ coefficient	.121	.208	.349*	.153	.328*
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.237	.109	.017	.183	.024
	N	37	37	37	37	37
Reasons of level 4 of C5	ρ coefficient	-.240	-.031	.123	.169	.194
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.076	.428	.235	.158	.125
	N	37	37	37	37	37
Reasons of level 5 of C5	ρ coefficient	.061	.015	-.006	-.038	-.046
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.359	.465	.485	.411	.393
	N	37	37	37	37	37
Egocentric reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	-.138	-.191	-.393**	-.351*	-.467**
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.207	.129	.008	.017	.002
	N	37	37	37	37	37
Altruistic reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	.203	.031	.093	.265	.188
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.115	.428	.293	.056	.132
	N	37	37	37	37	37
Mixed reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	-.006	.176	.317*	.129	.302*
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.485	.149	.028	.224	.035
	N	37	37	37	37	37
Avoidance reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	-.162	.048	.202	.167	.243
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.169	.390	.115	.161	.073
	N	37	37	37	37	37
Approach reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	.162	-.048	-.202	-.167	-.243
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.169	.390	.115	.161	.073
	N	37	37	37	37	37

* $p < .05$ ** $p < .01$

Table 7
Rank Spearman correlations of C5 variables with the SRMS scores for each item of SRM-SFO

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Reasons of level 1 of C5	ρ coefficient	-.225	-.295*	-.431**	-.097	-.199	-.242	-.324*	-.432**	-.216
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.093	.043	.005	.287	.126	.071	.027	.003	.106
	<i>N</i>	36	35	35	36	38	36	38	38	35
Reasons of level 2 of C5	ρ coefficient	-.347*	-.270	-.217	-.056	-.305*	-.082	-.141	-.560**	-.247
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.016	.053	.098	.369	.033	.308	.200	.000	.070
	<i>N</i>	38	37	37	38	37	40	38	40	37
Reasons of level 3 of C5	ρ coefficient	-.276*	-.277*	-.256	.037	.079	.004	-.242	-.330*	-.057
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.047	.049	.063	.413	.322	.490	.071	.019	.370
	<i>N</i>	38	37	37	38	37	40	38	40	37
Reasons of level 4 of C5	ρ coefficient	-.093	-.200	-.050	.366*	.107	.156	-.072	-.068	.178
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.289	.118	.384	.012	.264	.168	.333	.339	.145
	<i>N</i>	38	37	37	38	37	40	38	40	37
Reasons of level 5 of C5	ρ coefficient	-.031	-.161	-.219	.268	.072	.073	-.358*	-.158	.017
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.427	.171	.096	.054	.339	.329	.015	.168	.460
	<i>N</i>	38	37	37	37	36	39	37	39	36
Egocentric reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	-.212	-.255	-.446**	.012	-.232	-.149	-.241	-.442**	-.212
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.107	.070	.004	.473	.090	.186	.078	.003	.111
	<i>N</i>	36	35	35	36	35	38	36	38	35
Altruistic reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	-.110	-.261	-.196	.274	.040	.077	-.341*	-.215	-.008
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.255	.059	.122	.050	.409	.321	.020	.095	.483
	<i>N</i>	38	37	37	37	36	39	37	39	36
Mixed reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	-.265	-.267	-.195	.072	.145	.021	-.208	-.294*	.009
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.054	.055	.124	.335	.197	.449	.106	.033	.479
	<i>N</i>	38	37	37	38	37	40	38	40	37
Avoidance reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	-.166	-.219	-.205	.161	.098	.090	-.298*	-.262	.071
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.159	.096	.111	.168	.282	.290	.034	.051	.337
	<i>N</i>	38	37	37	38	37	40	38	40	37

* $p < .05$ ** $p < .01$

Table 8
Rank Spearman correlations of C5 variables Rank Spearman correlations of C5 ipsatized variables
with the SRMS scores for each item of M-SFO

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Reasons of level 1 of C5	p coefficient	.061	.005	-.002	-.334*	-.165	-.341*	-.041	-.123	.018	.016
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.361	.488	.496	.025	.176	.019	.406	.235	.459	.463
Reasons of level 2 of C5	N	36	35	35	35	34	37	35	37	34	37
	p coefficient	-.213	.035	.020	-.340*	-.323*	-.195	.052	-.401**	-.241	.018
Reasons of level 3 of C5	Sig. (1-tailed)	.106	.421	.454	.023	.031	.124	.384	.007	.085	.457
	N	36	35	35	35	34	37	35	37	34	37
Reasons of level 4 of C5	p coefficient	-.228	-.102	-.098	-.058	.193	.099	-.012	-.087	-.125	-.186
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.091	.279	.288	.371	.137	.280	.473	.304	.240	.135
Reasons of level 5 of C5	N	36	35	35	35	34	37	35	37	34	37
	p coefficient	.092	.009	.207	.420**	.183	.219	.262	.235	.391*	-.036
Egocentric reasons of C5	Sig. (1-tailed)	.297	.480	.117	.006	.150	.097	.064	.081	.011	.416
	N	36	35	35	35	34	37	35	37	34	37
Altruistic reasons of C5	p coefficient	.076	-.034	-.197	.254	.088	.074	-.328*	-.052	-.012	.024
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.329	.423	.129	.071	.310	.332	.027	.380	.474	.444
Mixed reasons of C5	N	36	35	35	35	34	37	35	37	34	37
	p coefficient	-.066	.004	-.126	-.135	-.255	-.289*	-.021	-.332*	-.052	.043
Egocentric reasons of C5	Sig. (1-tailed)	.351	.490	.235	.219	.073	.042	.453	.022	.386	.399
	N	36	35	35	35	34	37	35	37	34	37
Altruistic reasons of C5	p coefficient	.282*	.029	.181	.253	.182	.172	-.079	.356*	.081	.199
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.048	.435	.150	.072	.152	.155	.326	.015	.324	.118
Mixed reasons of C5	N	36	35	35	35	34	37	35	37	34	37
	p coefficient	-.220	-.140	-.035	-.069	.330*	.064	.089	.032	.053	-.203
Avoidance reasons of C5	Sig. (1-tailed)	.099	.212	.421	.348	.028	.352	.306	.425	.383	.115
	N	36	35	35	35	34	37	35	37	34	37
Approach reasons of C5	p coefficient	.045	.078	-.073	.108	.329*	.207	.004	.249	.069	.057
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.396	.328	.338	.269	.029	.109	.492	.069	.276	.438
Mean of C5 (tendency to hide the truth)	N	36	35	35	35	34	37	35	37	34	37
	p coefficient	-.045	-.078	.073	-.108	-.329*	-.207	-.004	-.249	-.069	.057
Mean of C5 (tendency to hide the truth)	Sig. (1-tailed)	.396	.328	.338	.269	.029	.109	.492	.069	.276	.438
	N	36	35	35	35	34	37	35	37	34	37
Mean of C5 (tendency to hide the truth)	p coefficient	.061	.005	-.002	-.334*	-.165	-.341*	-.041	-.123	.018	.016
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.361	.488	.496	.025	.176	.019	.406	.235	.459	.463
Mean of C5 (tendency to hide the truth)	N	36	35	35	35	34	37	35	37	34	37

* $p < .05$ ** $p < .01$

Table 9
Rank Spearman correlations of C5 variables with the moral reasoning stage of the
“closest” answer for each item of SRM-SFO

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Reasons of level 1 of C5	p coefficient	-.157	-.285*	-.449**	-.004	-.107	-.333*	-.477**	-.502**	-.068	-.129
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.170	.039	.002	.490	.260	.017	.001	.000	.342	.213
	N	39	39	41	38	41	38	40	38	40	38
Reasons of level 2 of C5	p coefficient	-.365**	-.363**	-.392**	.090	-.226	-.233	-.336*	-.547**	-.081	-.182
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.010	.010	.006	.282	.080	.067	.017	.000	.311	.125
	N	41	41	40	43	40	43	40	42	40	42
Reasons of level 3 of C5	p coefficient	-.145	-.189	-.351*	.122	.078	-.113	-.372**	-.397**	.025	-.225
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.183	.119	.013	.217	.316	.236	.009	.005	.440	.076
	N	41	41	40	43	40	43	40	42	40	42
Reasons of level 4 of C5	p coefficient	-.236	-.194	-.125	.300*	.154	.055	-.127	-.073	.258	-.137
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.069	.112	.220	.025	.171	.562	.217	.324	.054	.193
	N	41	41	40	43	40	43	40	42	40	42
Reasons of level 5 of C5	p coefficient	-.083	-.262	-.204	.226	.071	.027	-.368*	-.209	.104	-.018
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.305	.051	.106	.078	.334	.434	.011	.097	.267	.457
	N	40	40	39	41	39	41	39	40	38	41
Egocentric reasons of C5	p coefficient	-.207	-.326*	-.506**	.088	-.172	-.233	-.396**	-.481**	-.067	-.082
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.103	.021	.001	.294	.151	.074	.007	.001	.347	.307
	N	39	39	38	40	38	40	38	39	37	40
Altruistic reasons of C5	p coefficient	-.156	-.286*	-.192	.248	.040	-.023	-.354*	-.272*	.075	-.048
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.168	.037	.121	.057	.404	.441	.014	.043	.325	.383
	N	40	40	39	42	39	42	39	41	39	41
Mixed reasons of C5	p coefficient	-.179	-.240	-.312*	.140	.148	-.081	-.341*	-.354*	.098	-.240
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.131	.066	.025	.186	.181	.303	.016	.011	.274	.063
	N	41	41	40	43	40	43	40	42	40	42
Avoidance reasons of C5	p coefficient	-.210	-.237	-.261	.139	.125	.019	-.386**	-.290*	.178	-.142
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.093	.068	.052	.190	.222	.454	.007	.033	.139	.186
	N	41	41	40	42	40	42	40	41	39	42
Approach reasons of C5	p coefficient	-.214	-.302*	-.418**	.166	-.126	-.209	-.418**	-.491**	-.089	-.102
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.099	.033	.005	.153	.229	.097	.005	.001	.301	.267
	N	38	38	37	40	37	40	37	39	37	39
Mean of C5 (tendency to hide the truth)	p coefficient	-.193	-.240	-.377*	.116	.018	-.107	-.378*	-.396**	.054	-.088
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.123	.073	.011	.242	.457	.259	.011	.007	.377	.296
	N	38	38	37	39	37	39	37	38	36	39

* $p < .05$ ** $p < .01$

Table 10
Rank Spearman correlations of C5 ipsatized variables with the moral reasoning stage of the "closest" answer for each item of SRM-SFO

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Reasons of level 1 of C5	p coefficient Sig. (1-tailed) N	.094 .287 38	.212 .101 38	.065 .351 37	-.325* .022 39	-.063 .356 37	-.282* .041 39	-.013 .469 37	-.073 .331 38	-.004 .491 36	.009 .478 39
Reasons of level 2 of C5	p coefficient Sig. (1-tailed) N	-.279* .045 38	-.130 .217 38	-.104 .271 37	-.174 .145 39	-.232 .084 37	-.242 .069 39	-.027 .438 37	-.337* .019 38	-.140 .208 36	-.001 .498 39
Reasons of level 3 of C5	p coefficient Sig. (1-tailed) N	-.059 .363 38	.067 .345 38	-.103 .271 37	.012 .471 39	.134 .214 37	.058 .362 39	-.102 .274 37	-.081 .315 38	-.137 .213 36	-.220 .089 39
Reasons of level 4 of C5	p coefficient Sig. (1-tailed) N	.460 .017 38	.479 -.009 38	.235 .123 37	.068 .243 39	.092 .223 37	.090 .219 39	.054 .269 37	.047 .276* 38	.007 .409** 36	.307 -.083 39
Reasons of level 5 of C5	p coefficient Sig. (1-tailed) N	.014 .466 38	-.201 .113 38	-.136 .211 37	.227 .082 39	.070 .341 37	.063 .353 39	-.311* .030 37	-.133 .212 38	.066 .351 36	.109 .255 39
Egocentric reasons of C5	p coefficient Sig. (1-tailed) N	-.112 .252 38	-.067 .345 38	-.211 .105 37	-.033 .421 39	-.173 .153 37	-.317* .025 39	-.084 .310 37	-.322* .024 38	-.031 .429 36	.028 .433 39
Altruistic reasons of C5	p coefficient Sig. (1-tailed) N	.180 .139 38	.017 .459 38	.358* .015 37	.084 .305 39	.120 .239 37	.244 .067 39	.124 .231 37	.332* .021 38	.068 .348 36	.287* .038 39
Mixed reasons of C5	p coefficient Sig. (1-tailed) N	-.102 .271 38	.013 .470 38	-.098 .282 37	-.032 .424 39	.259 .061 37	.057 .365 39	-.004 .490 37	.026 .438 38	.042 .404 36	-.278* .044 39
Avoidance reasons of C5	p coefficient Sig. (1-tailed) N	.030 .429 38	.021 .451 38	-.084 .311 37	.063 .351 39	.279* .047 37	.212 .098 39	-.022 .448 37	.179 .141 38	.299* .038 36	-.057 .364 39
Approach reasons of C5	p coefficient Sig. (1-tailed) N	-.030 .429 38	-.021 .451 38	.084 .311 37	-.063 .351 39	-.279* .047 37	-.212 .098 39	.022 .448 37	-.179 .141 38	-.299* .038 36	.057 .364 39

* $p < .05$ ** $p < .01$

Table 11
 Rank Spearman correlations of C5 variables with the mean moral reasoning stage of the “close” answers for each item of SRM-SFO

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Reasons of level 1 of C5	p coefficient	-.289*	-.231	-.027	-.101	-.240	-.038	.100	-.070	-.329*	
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.041 37	.088 36	.435 38	.279 36	.073 38	.410 38	.275 38	.339 38	.023 37	.134 38
Reasons of level 2 of C5	p coefficient	-.178	-.225	.336*	-.087	-.349*	.232	.324*	-.413**	-.029	
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.138 39	.088 38	.017 40	.301 38	.014 40	.221 40	.074 40	.021 40	.004 39	.430 39
Reasons of level 3 of C5	p coefficient	-.290*	-.232	.071	.062	.019	.109	.004	-.067	-.221	-.062
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.037 39	.080 38	.332 40	.355 38	.453 40	.251 40	.490 40	.340 40	.088 39	.353 39
Reasons of level 4 of C5	p coefficient	-.058	-.245	.311*	.270	.026	.129	.078	-.100	.039	-.045
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.364 39	.069 38	.026 40	.051 38	.438 40	.214 40	.317 40	.269 40	.406 39	.392 39
Reasons of level 5 of C5	p coefficient	-.113	-.177	-.013	.093	.025	.064	-.094	-.019	-.086	-.143
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.247 39	.144 38	.470 39	.292 37	.440 38	.349 39	.286 39	.454 39	.303 38	.195 38
Egocentric reasons of C5	p coefficient	-.212	-.209	.056	-.090	-.348*	.029	.182	-.106	-.357*	-.115
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.104 37	.111 36	.372 37	.300 36	.017 37	.432 38	.136 38	.264 38	.015 37	.245 38
Altruistic reasons of C5	p coefficient	-.165	-.290*	.018	.147	.030	.074	-.073	-.089	-.147	-.150
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.157 39	.039 38	.455 40	.192 37	.427 39	.327 39	.329 39	.296 39	.189 38	.184 38
Mixed reasons of C5	p coefficient	-.250	-.223	.159	.107	.046	.093	.015	-.074	-.168	-.077
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.062 39	.089 38	.164 40	.262 38	.388 40	.285 40	.464 40	.325 40	.153 39	.320 39
Avoidance reasons of C5	p coefficient	-.174	-.227	.073	.096	.042	.116	-.023	-.088	-.131	-.101
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.144 39	.086 38	.330 39	.283 38	.400 39	.237 40	.444 40	.294 40	.214 39	.271 39
Approach reasons of C5	p coefficient	-.286*	-.250	.065	-.061	-.228	.025	.107	-.108	-.404**	-.153
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.043 37	.070 36	.349 38	.364 35	.087 37	.442 37	.264 37	.262 37	.007 36	.184 37
Mean of C5 (tendency to hide the truth)	p coefficient	-.246	-.221	.014	-.017	-.163	.070	.116	-.033	-.273	-.143
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.071 37	.097 36	.468 37	.461 35	.171 36	.340 37	.248 37	.423 37	.054 36	.200 37

* $p < .05$ ** $p < .01$

Table 12
 Rank Spearman correlations of C5 ipsatized variables with the mean moral reasoning stage of the “close” answers
 for each item of SRM-SFO

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Reasons of level 1 of C5	ρ coefficient	-.050	-.069	-.226	-.189	-.268	-.242	.005	-.093	.050	-.083
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.384 37	.344 36	.089 37	.138 35	.057 36	.074 37	.488 37	.292 37	.387 36	.312 37
Reasons of level 2 of C5	ρ coefficient	.035	.080	.332*	-.302*	-.510**	.001	.294*	-.346*	-.335*	.133
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.418 37	.321 36	.022 37	.039 35	.001 36	.499 37	.039 37	.018 37	.023 36	.216 37
Reasons of level 3 of C5	ρ coefficient	-.263	-.041	-.112	.001	.237	.147	-.051	.024	-.135	.001
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.058 37	.405 36	.255 37	.497 35	.082 36	.193 37	.382 37	.443 37	.217 36	.498 37
Reasons of level 4 of C5	ρ coefficient	.116	-.060	.277*	.495**	.093	.082	.122	.034	.288*	.007
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.247 37	.365 36	.049 37	.001 35	.295 36	.315 37	.235 37	.420 37	.044 36	.484 37
Reasons of level 5 of C5	ρ coefficient	-.073	-.061	-.084	.022	-.044	-.004	-.113	-.086	-.084	-.121
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.335 37	.362 36	.310 37	.451 35	.400 36	.491 37	.252 37	.306 37	.312 36	.238 37
Egocentric reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	.139	.009	.159	-.171	-.511**	-.051	.229	-.210	-.108	.039
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.207 37	.480 36	.174 37	.163 35	.001 36	.383 37	.087 37	.106 37	.266 36	.409 37
Altruistic reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	.075	-.087	-.265	.163	.309*	-.147	-.242	.151	.164	-.065
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.330 37	.306 36	.056 37	.175 35	.033 36	.193 37	.075 37	.186 37	.170 36	.351 37
Mixed reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	-.195	-.022	.052	.022	.266	.067	-.055	.104	.011	.030
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.124 37	.449 36	.380 37	.449 35	.058 36	.348 37	.374 37	.270 37	.474 36	.431 37
Avoidance reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	-.009	.096	-.018	.155	.397**	.100	-.097	.331*	.208	.028
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.479 37	.289 36	.457 37	.187 35	.008 36	.277 37	.283 37	.023 37	.112 36	.434 37
Approach reasons of C5	ρ coefficient	.009	-.096	.018	-.155	-.397**	-.100	.097	-.331*	-.208	-.028
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.479 37	.289 36	.457 37	.187 35	.008 36	.277 37	.283 37	.023 37	.112 36	.434 37

* $p < .05$ ** $p < .01$

Table 13
Rank Spearman correlations of C2 variables with the MVE score of SRM-SFO

	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5	Egocentric reasons scale of C2	Altruistic reasons scale of C2	Mean score of 1-30 items of C2	Item 31 of C2
MVE of SRM-SFO									
p coefficient	-.534**	-.312	-.318	-.486**	-.424*	-.477**	-.489**	-.501**	.041
Sig. (1-tailed)	.002	.061	.053	.005	.014	.007	.005	.005	.420
N	27	26	27	27	27	26	27	25	27

* $p < .05$ ** $p < .01$

Table 14

Rank Spearman correlations of the score of C2 for reasons for hiding the truth of level 2 with the global scores for moral reasoning of SRM-SFO

	SRMS	Mean of SRMS of each item of SRMS-SFO	Mean of the mean stage of "close" answers at each item of SRMS-SFO	Mean of the stage of "closest" answers at each item of SRMS-SFO	Mean of the stage of all "close" answers of SRMS-SFO
Reasons of level 2 of C2					
p coefficient	-.401*	-.422*	-.634**	-.228	-.550**
Sig. (1-tailed)	.029	.041	.001	.141	.001
N	23	18	22	24	27

* $p < .05$ ** $p < .01$

Table 15
Rank Spearman correlations of C2 variables with the scores for the preferred stages of moral reasoning of the “close” and “closest” answers at SRM-SFO

		Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5	Egocentric reasons scale of C2	Altruistic reasons scale of C2	Mean score of 1-30 items of C2	Item 31 of C2
Stage 1 closest	p coefficient	-.370*	.102	-.182	-.295	-.278	-.254	-.298	-.293	.031
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.041	.326	.202	.086	.099	.127	.084	.099	.444
Stage 2 closest	p coefficient	-.037	.283	-.064	.300	.078	-.072	.171	.038	.099
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.398	.101	.386	.082	.362	.375	.217	.435	.326
Stage 3 closest	p coefficient	.348	.191	.237	.477*	.301	.291	.410*	.391*	.169
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.052	.198	.139	.011	.081	.095	.026	.040	.220
Stage 4 closest	p coefficient	.008	-.306	-.035	-.281	-.067	.000	-.173	-.081	-.270
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.485	.083	.438	.097	.381	.500	.216	.363	.107
Percentage of stage 3 and 4 of “closest” answers	p coefficient	.318	-.230	.222	-.011	.159	.268	.104	.213	-.148
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.069	.152	.154	.479	.235	.114	.318	.177	.249
Stage 1 close	p coefficient	-.038	.366*	.152	.076	-.103	.121	-.037	.061	.005
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.387	.033	.224	.353	.304	.278	.426	.386	.490
Stage 2 close	p coefficient	-.050	.443*	.251	-.011	-.020	.173	-.011	.106	.074
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.401	.012	.103	.477	.461	.199	.479	.308	.557
Stage 3 close	p coefficient	-.241	.264	-.117	-.031	-.187	-.147	-.125	-.159	-.063
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.113	.096	.281	.439	.175	.237	.268	.224	.377
Stage 4 close	p coefficient	-.104	-.318	.051	-.345*	-.086	-.113	-.182	-.176	-.153
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.304	.057	.401	.039	.335	.291	.182	.201	.223
Percentage of stage 3 and 4 of “close” answers	p coefficient	-.201	.156	-.072	-.081	-.181	-.129	-.139	-.147	-.016
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.157	.223	.361	.344	.182	.265	.244	.242	.469
	N	27	26	27	27	27	26	27	25	27

* $p < .05$ ** $p < .01$

Table 16
Rank Spearman correlations of C2 variables with the MVE score of each item of SRM-SFO

	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5	Egocentric reasons scale of C2	Altruistic reasons scale of C2	Mean score of 1-30 items of C2	Item 31 of C2
MVE for item 1 of SRM-SFO	ρ coefficient	-.276	-.131	-.192	-.020	-.212	-.065	-.151	-.024
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.070	.246	.154	.459	.135	.367	.222	.449
MVE for item 2 of SRM-SFO	ρ coefficient	.008	-.016	-.118	-.156	-.004	-.158	-.097	-.059
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.483	.467	.268	.206	.491	.201	.311	.378
MVE for item 3 of SRM-SFO	ρ coefficient	-.138	-.046	.000	-.059	-.061	-.032	-.022	-.267
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.234	.405	.500	.379	.376	.433	.457	.077
MVE for item 4 of SRM-SFO	ρ coefficient	-.537**	-.300**	-.423**	-.452**	-.549**	-.484**	-.575**	.134
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.001	.065	.002	.010	.006	.003	.001	.241
MVE for item 5 of SRM-SFO	ρ coefficient	-.380*	-.307	-.296	-.187	-.437*	-.236	-.336*	-.042
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.021	.019	.053	.059	.166	.109	.043	.415
MVE for item 6 of SRM-SFO	ρ coefficient	-.033	-.166	.039	.000	.163	.129	.036	-.267
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.432	.195	.419	.500	.195	.248	.428	.077
MVE for item 7 of SRM-SFO	ρ coefficient	.209	-.335*	.173	.000	.231	.163	.183	.117
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.133	.038	.180	.500	.110	.194	.176	.270
MVE for item 8 of SRM-SFO	ρ coefficient	-.616**	-.337*	-.330*	-.470**	-.516**	-.553**	-.602**	-.074
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.000	.037	.038	.004	.002	.001	.000	.348
MVE for item 9 of SRM-SFO	ρ coefficient	-.235	.083	-.227	-.181	-.164	-.183	-.241	.258
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.110	.337	.118	.174	.197	.171	.113	.088
MVE for item 10 of SRM-SFO	ρ coefficient	-.346*	.129	-.162	-.238	-.081	-.134	-.227	-.288
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.036	.261	.205	.112	.341	.248	.132	.069
		28	27	28	28	27	28	26	28

* $p < .05$ ** $p < .01$

Table 17
Rank Spearman correlations of C2 variables with the SRMS score of each item of SRM-SFO

	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5	Egocentric reasons scale of C2	Altruistic reasons scale of C2	Mean score of 1-30 items of C2	Item 31 of C2
MVE for item 1 of SRM-SFO	p coefficient	-.276	-.131	-.192	-.020	-.212	-.065	-.151	-.024
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.070	.246	.154	.459	.135	.367	.222	.449
	N	30	30	30	30	29	30	28	30
MVE for item 2 of SRM-SFO	p coefficient	-.008	-.016	-.118	-.156	-.004	-.158	-.097	-.059
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.483	.467	.268	.206	.491	.201	.311	.378
	N	30	29	30	30	29	30	28	30
MVE for item 3 of SRM-SFO	p coefficient	-.138	-.113	-.046	.000	-.061	-.032	-.022	-.267
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.234	.280	.405	.500	.379	.433	.457	.077
	N	30	29	30	30	29	30	28	30
MVE for item 4 of SRM-SFO	p coefficient	-.537**	-.287	-.500**	-.423**	-.549**	-.484**	-.575**	.134
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.001	.065	.002	.010	.006	.003	.001	.241
	N	30	29	30	30	29	30	28	30
MVE for item 5 of SRM-SFO	p coefficient	-.380*	-.395*	-.307	-.296	-.437*	-.236	-.336*	-.042
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.021	.019	.053	.059	.166	.109	.043	.415
	N	29	28	29	29	28	29	27	29
MVE for item 6 of SRM-SFO	p coefficient	-.033	-.166	.039	.000	.163	.129	.036	-.267
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.432	.195	.419	.500	.195	.248	.428	.077
	N	30	29	30	30	29	30	28	30
MVE for item 7 of SRM-SFO	p coefficient	.209	-.335*	.173	.000	.231	.163	.183	.117
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.133	.038	.180	.500	.110	.194	.176	.270
	N	30	29	30	30	29	30	28	30
MVE for item 8 of SRM-SFO	p coefficient	-.616**	-.337*	-.330*	-.470**	-.516**	-.529**	-.602**	-.074
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.000	.037	.038	.004	.002	.001	.000	.348
	N	30	29	30	30	29	30	28	30
MVE for item 9 of SRM-SFO	p coefficient	-.235	.083	-.227	-.181	-.164	-.183	-.241	.258
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.110	.337	.118	.174	.197	.171	.113	.088
	N	29	28	29	29	28	29	27	29
MVE for item 10 of SRM-SFO	p coefficient	-.346*	.129	-.162	-.238	-.081	-.134	-.227	-.288
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.036	.261	.205	.112	.341	.248	.132	.069
	N	28	27	28	28	27	28	26	28

* $p < .05$ ** $p < .01$

Table 18
 Rank Spearman correlations of C2 variables with the moral reasoning stage of the “closest” answer for each item of SRM-SFO

		Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5	Egocentric reasons scale of C2	Altruistic reasons scale of C2	Mean score of 1-30 items of C2	Item 31 of C2
Stage of the “closest” answer for item 1	p coefficient	-.306	-.152	-.461**	-.354*	-.337*	-.350*	-.378*	-.409*	-.318*
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.053 29	.219 28	.006 29	.030 29	.037 29	.034 28	.021 29	.017 27	.046 29
Stage of the “closest” answer for item 2	p coefficient	.042	.245	.206	-.065	.134	.188	.069	.164	-.082
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.414 29	.104 28	.142 29	.369 29	.244 29	.169 28	.360 29	.207 27	.336 29
Stage of the “closest” answer for item 3	p coefficient	.314	-.139	.193	.293	.413*	.255	.389*	.364*	-.321*
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.052 28	.244 28	.162 28	.065 28	.015 27	.100 26	.020 27	.034 26	.048 28
Stage of the “closest” answer for item 4	p coefficient	.164	-.244	-.142	.112	.042	-.026	.059	-.028	.027
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.207 27	.115 26	.240 27	.289 27	.417 27	.450 26	.385 27	.448 25	.447 27
Stage of the “closest” answer for item 5	p coefficient	-.205	-.326	-.220	-.232	-.152	-.240	-.203	-.246	-.176
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.152 27	.052 26	.135 27	.122 27	.225 27	.119 26	.155 26	.118 25	.190 27
Stage of the “closest” answer for item 6	p coefficient	-.041	-.005	.212	-.286	-.228	.096	-.266	-.104	-.153
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.419 27	.490 26	.144 27	.074 27	.126 27	.320 26	.090 27	.311 25	.223 27
Stage of the “closest” answer for item 7	p coefficient	-.253	-.014	-.299	.098	-.353*	-.251	-.238	-.269	-.068
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.102 27	.474 26	.065 27	.313 27	.035 27	.108 26	.116 26	.096 25	.368 27
Stage of the “closest” answer for item 8	p coefficient	-.161	.065	-.048	-.074	.077	-.078	.030	-.005	-.198
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.203 29	.371 28	.402 29	.352 29	.345 29	.346 28	.439 29	.491 27	.152 29
Stage of the “closest” answer for item 9	p coefficient	.351*	-.035	.364*	.081	.281	.340*	.235	.320	.077
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.037 27	.433 26	.031 27	.344 27	.078 27	.044 26	.119 26	.059 25	.351 27
Stage of the “closest” answer for item 10	p coefficient	.157	-.065	.024	-.172	.184	.087	.073	.131	-.052
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.212 28	.373 27	.452 28	.190 28	.175 28	.332 27	.357 28	.261 26	.397 28

* $p < .05$ ** $p < .01$

Table 19
Rank Spearman correlations of C2 variables with the mean moral reasoning stage of the “close” answers for each item of SRM-SFO

		Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5	Egocentric reasons scale of C2	Altruistic reasons scale of C2	Mean score of 1-30 items of C2	Item 31 of C2
Mean stage of the “close” answers for item 1	ρ coefficient	-.327*	-.557**	-.435*	-.183	-.326*	-.425*	-.313	-.414*	-.137
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.045 28	.001 27	.010 28	.175 28	.045 28	.013 27	.053 28	.018 26	.244 28
Mean stage of the “close” answers for item 2	ρ coefficient	-.174	-.342*	-.096	.003	-.139	-.207	-.103	-.187	-.006
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.192 27	.044 26	.316 27	.494 27	.244 27	.155 26	.305 27	.185 25	.488 27
Mean stage of the “close” answers for item 3	ρ coefficient	.187	-.076	-.046	-.086	.278	.077	.161	.150	.040
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.165 29	.350 28	.406 29	.329 29	.072 29	.348 28	.201 29	.227 27	.419 29
Mean stage of the “close” answers for item 4	ρ coefficient	.178	-.149	-.001	-.185	.028	.060	-.030	.001	-.106
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.192 26	.239 25	.498 26	.183 26	.445 26	.388 25	.442 26	.498 24	.303 26
Mean stage of the “close” answers for item 5	ρ coefficient	-.068	-.158	-.117	-.060	-.070	-.099	-.097	-.121	-.063
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.363 29	.211 28	.273 29	.378 29	.359 29	.308 28	.309 29	.274 27	.372 29
Mean stage of the “close” answers for item 6	ρ coefficient	-.487**	-.287	-.350*	-.392*	-.375*	-.424*	-.431*	-.476**	-.267
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.004 28	.073 27	.034 28	.020 28	.025 28	.014 27	.011 28	.007 26	.085 28
Mean stage of the “close” answers for item 7	ρ coefficient	-.055	-.188	.040	-.031	-.051	-.054	-.048	-.072	-.081
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.390 28	.173 27	.420 28	.437 28	.399 28	.395 27	.404 28	.364 26	.342 28
Mean stage of the “close” answers for item 8	ρ coefficient	.106	-.516**	.102	.091	.164	.042	.149	.116	-.006
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.303 26	.004 25	.310 26	.329 26	.211 26	.421 25	.234 26	.295 24	.488 26
Mean stage of the “close” answers for item 9	ρ coefficient	.224	-.427*	.162	-.010	.307	.102	.204	.179	-.245
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.141 25	.019 24	.220 25	.482 25	.068 25	.317 24	.164 25	.207 23	.119 25
Mean stage of the “close” answers for item 10	ρ coefficient	.101	-.242	-.103	.012	.039	-.046	.029	.020	.089
	Sig. (1-tailed) N	.308 27	.117 26	.304 27	.476 27	.385 27	.412 26	.443 27	.462 25	.329 27

* $p < .05$ ** $p < .01$

In order to compare the results from the current study with the ones from Faiciuc (2020), and Faiciuc (2016a), an analysis was made also at the level of the C5 items. Its results are presented in Tables 20, and 21 (Appendix 3).

DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

With few exceptions, the scales of the used instruments had at least acceptable coefficients of internal consistency, for most of them exceeding the value of 0.7.

Relationship of the general score of C5 (willingness to hie the truth), and, respectively, of C2 (tendency to consider hiding the truth as justified) with the general and item scores of SRM-SFO that indicate moral reasoning maturity and moral value evaluation

Regarding the first general hypothesis, data indicated that the general score of C5 (interpreted as the general tendency to hide the truth) correlated negatively statistically significantly, as it was predicted, or as tendency with four out of the five general scores of SRM-SFO that indicate the level of general moral maturity (with the mean of the SRMS scores of each item of SRM-SFO, mean of the stage of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO, significantly, and, as a tendency, with SRMS, and with the mean of the stage of the “close” answers of each item of SRM-SFO), especially with the ones that were based on the moral stage of the “closest” answers, i.e. when moral maturity was assessed based on a forced choice. These results indicate that the synthetic scores for the moral reasoning maturity computed based on the SRM-SFO answers have a stronger association with the tendency to hide the truth than moral competence, as defined by Lind (1978), because in Faiciuc (2016a), and Faiciuc (2020) the expected negative correlation of the computed moral competence index, as a synthetic measure for the principled moral reasoning and, indirectly, for the principled moral behavior, with the tendency to hide the truth, no matter the reason, was not obtained. On the contrary, their correlation tended to be a positive one, becoming statistically significant for some participants with certain emotion regulation characteristics. The above-mentioned results indicate also that the self-reported tendency to hide the truth when assessed by taking into consideration the conditions/reasons in which the respondent is or would be willing to disengage from the observance of the particular moral norm of telling the truth has a link (even though not a strong one) with her/his general level of mature moral reasoning when justifying the importance of various moral norms, in general. So, in the present study, the obtained data are compatible with the idea that truth telling/hiding, no matter the situation, may be considered as an epitome of the moral behavior, being representative for a general mature moral judgment.

Instead, the general score of C5 did not correlate statistically significantly with the general moral value evaluation score (MVE). So, the predicted negative association between the general tendency/willingness to hide the truth and the general importance attributed to the moral values assessed with SRM-SFO was not supported by data. In this regard, an unexpected result was obtained, as the general score of C5 correlated (as a tendency, positively, not negatively as it was expected) solely with the importance attributed to the tenth moral value assessed with SRM-SFO, i.e. **“judges sending people who break the law to jail”**. So, the prediction that the general tendency to hide the truth should be negatively associated with the importance attributed to the moral value of **“telling the truth” (item 4)** was not supported by data, too. It is a result that may indicate that the self-reported tendency to hide the truth has a stronger association with the level of moral reasoning than with the importance attributed to moral values, even with the importance of the one with which it has a direct link: telling the truth. Alternatively, the absence of the expected correlations with the moral value evaluation of the self-reported tendency to hide the truth may be linked with fact that the importance of the moral values had low variability, as it was investigated with a Likert scale with only three values, and the “not important” answer was very rarely chosen by the respondents. This result may suggest also that the involvement of social desirability in responding at the C5 items might not have been a significant one, in the case in which the answers at SRM-SFO that assessed the importance of the investigated moral values were strongly influenced by social desirability (as it suggested by the low frequency of the “not important” answer). If social desirability would have been influenced the answers of both instruments, the general tendency to lie as measured with C5 and the importance attributed to the moral values investigated with SRM-SFO should have had a significant negative correlation.

As predicted, the general score of C5 correlated negatively statistically significantly with the scores that indicate the preference for a mature moral reasoning, when participants were forced to choose only one moral argument (preference for moral arguments of level 4 of the “closest” answers, and the percentage of “closest” answers of level 3 and 4). Instead, in the same condition, it did not correlate positively with the preference for the immature moral argumentation. It occurred only a tendency for such a positive association between the tendency to hide the truth and the preference for moral arguments of level 2, which indicates an instrumental morality, focused on the reciprocal bargain. Also, the predicted correlations between the preference for the mature or immature moral argumentation when assessed with the “close” answers at SRM-SFO and the score of C5 that indicates the general tendency to hide the truth were not obtained either. In Faiciuc (2020), the correlations of the score of C5 for the general tendency to hide the truth with the preference for each of the six levels of moral reasoning assessed with the Moral Competence Test (MCT, Lind, 1978) were not presented.

Unexpectedly, the above-mentioned C5 score correlated statistically significantly positively with the mean preference for all the moral arguments of MCT ($\rho = .247$, $p = .02$, $N = 90$, two-tailed), suggesting the possible influence of a response bias in the generation of this result (e.g., acceptance tendency or/and social desirability). This influence was supported by a supplementary result, given that, using the principal component analysis for the preference scores for each of the six levels of moral reasoning assessed with MCT, only one component resulted, which had large positive associations with all the above-mentioned six preference scores. The above-mentioned unexpected positive correlation was mainly due to the statistically significant positive correlation of the score of C5 for the general tendency to hide the truth with the preference for the pre-conventional moral reasoning of level 1 ($\rho = .272$, $p = .005$, $N = 91$, one-tailed), with the preference for the conventional moral reasoning of level 3 ($\rho = .189$, $p = .034$, $N = 94$, one-tailed), with the preference for the post-conventional moral reasoning of level 4 ($\rho = .228$, $p = .014$, $N = 94$, one-tailed), and its tendency to correlate positively with the preference for the post-conventional moral reasoning of level 5 ($\rho = .143$, $p = .086$, $N = 93$, one-tailed). It only tended to correlate negatively, as expected, with the ipsatized score of the preference for the sixth level of moral reasoning assessed with MCT ($\rho = -.15$, $p = .079$, $N = 90$, one-tailed). In Faiciuc (2016a), the corresponding results tended to be the same as in Faiciuc (2020). They also were not presented in Faiciuc (2016a). On the data from Faiciuc (2016a), the score of C5 for the general tendency to hide the truth correlated positively marginally with the mean preference for all the moral arguments of MCT ($\rho = .268$, $p = .052$, $N = 38$, one-tailed), and with the preference for the pre-conventional moral reasoning of level 1 ($\rho = .223$, $p = .039$, $N = 38$, one-tailed), with the preference for the conventional moral reasoning of level 3 ($\rho = .253$, $p = .06$, $N = 94$, one-tailed), with the preference for the post-conventional moral reasoning of level 4 ($\rho = .225$, $p = .084$, $N = 39$, one-tailed), and correlated statistically significantly positively with the relative preference for the conventional moral reasoning of level 3 ($\rho = .276$, $p = .047$, $N = 38$, one-tailed).

Given the above-mentioned results, it seems that the association of the general self-reported tendency to hide the truth as assessed with C5 with the preference for the different levels/stages of moral reasoning that follow the basic structure of the Kohlbergian theory depends on the kind of instrument that it is used for its assessment. The results obtained with SRM-SFO seem closer to the expected ones. For SRM-SFO, the expected association was stronger with the preference for the post-conventional moral reasoning, whereas, for MCT, the expected association was stronger with the preference for the pre-conventional moral reasoning. In the same time, for MCT, the unexpected positive association of the tendency to hide the truth with the preference for moral arguments placed at a post-conventional level may be explained by the answer format of MCT (*i.e.*, the answers on Likert scales with nine points, which do not force the respondents to

directly choose one moral argument over another), which may favor to a greater extent the occurrence of some response biases than the answer format of the SRM-SFO in its part linked with the “closest” answers. In fact, for SRM-SFO, too, a similar difference exists between the results obtained with the scores of SRM-SFO computed based on the “close” answers and those obtained with the scores of SRM-SFO computed based on the “closest” answers, because the “closest” answers do not allow the influence of the responses biases to the same extent as the “close” answers.

The detailed analysis suggests that the tendency to hide the truth assessed with C5 may be negatively associated particularly with the stage of moral reasoning of “closest” answers used for supporting the importance of moral values of **“keeping promises to a child” (item 3)**, and **“not taking away things that belong to others”, i.e. item 8**, (which are moral values that, when transgressed, hiding the truth is likely involved), and, to a lesser extent, with the stage of moral reasoning of “closest” answers used for supporting the importance of moral values of **“saving the life of a stranger” (item 7)** or **“keeping a promise to a person you hardly know”, i.e. item 2** (which are moral values in which the moral behavior toward strangers is considered, as an indication of a general higher commitment to moral values as care and fairness). A similar pattern of results occurred for the correlation between the C5 global score and the SRMS score for each item of SRM-SFO, as it correlated negatively significantly with SRMS score for the **item 3 (“keeping promises to a child”)**, and with the SRMS score of **item 8 (“not taking away things that belong to others”)**, and tended to correlate negatively with the SRMS score for **item 7 (“saving the life of a stranger”)**, and **item 2 (“keeping a promise to a person you hardly know”)**. In the same time, the C5 global score, assessing the tendency to hide the truth, did not correlate as expected statistically significantly with the mean stage of moral reasoning of “close” answers at SRM-SFO, but only tended to correlate negatively with the mean stage of moral reasoning for “close” answers used to support the importance of moral value of **“keeping promises to friends” (item 1)**, or **“obeying the law” (item 9)**. It is notable that the score of C5 assessing the tendency to hide the truth in general did not correlate with the preferred level of moral reasoning for supporting the moral value of telling the truth, in spite of the expectation that they should be associated based on the direct link between telling the truth and hiding the truth. In general, the correlations discussed above were weak or moderate. The above-mentioned results suggest that the tendency to hide the truth, no matter the reason, may be linked not so much with the content domain of the truth telling in what regards the level of moral reasoning, but with the level of moral argumentation for the moral values investigated with SRM-SFO that involve situations in which the social obligation or control regarding their observance may be perceived to be at a lower level (like the behaviors toward children, strangers, or when one has the occasion to steal without being seen).

In opposition with the case of C5, for C2, the total score (indicating the general tendency to consider hiding the truth justified) correlated, as predicted, significantly negatively with MVE score, assessing the general importance attributed to moral values assessed with SRM-SFO, but, unexpectedly, not with the SRM-SFO scores that assess the general level of maturity of moral reasoning. However, data support partially some relationship between the total score of C2 and the maturity of the moral reasoning, but in the opposite direction than the predicted one, as the total score of C2 correlated positively statistically significantly with the preference for the mature moral reasoning of stage 3 of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO, and negatively with the preference for the immature moral reasoning of stage 1 of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO. For C2, on the data from Faiciuc (2016a), too, the score of C2 indicating the general tendency to consider hiding the truth as justified tended to correlate, unexpectedly, positively with the preference for the postconventional moral reasoning of level 5 ($\rho = .267, p = .089, N = 27$, one-tailed), and correlated statistically significantly positively with the relative preference for the postconventional moral reasoning of level 5 ($\rho = .327, p = .048, N = 27$, one-tailed). The above-mentioned score of C2 did not correlate statistically significantly with the mean preference for all the moral arguments of MCT. So, in contrast with the general score of C5, the general score of C2 seem to be more linked with the evaluation of the investigated moral values than to the general level of moral reasoning in justifying those moral values. The way C2 items were formulated and their response format may have contributed to this result. Because of the impersonal nuance in the meaning of the C2 items and the forced choice of approval or disapproval of the given statements, the answers to the C2 items seem to express, at least partially, the perception of a respondent regarding the acceptability of hiding the truth as a moral value in her/his community in the mentioned situations or her/his reflection or expectations regarding hiding the truth in general or regarding the behavior of other people in their relationship with the respondent, and not only the way that respondent behaves or would behave regarding the truth telling in the situations that were taken into consideration both in C5, and C2. It may be that the MVE score of SRM-SFO express also partially the same perception regarding the truth telling as a moral value in the respondent’s community and her/his expectations regarding the truth telling of other people in their relationship with her/him. The preference for the lower stages of postconventional reasoning assessed both with MCT, and SRM-SFO seem to be linked with a higher acceptability regarding hiding the truth. This result may be put in relationship with a result of Makowski *et al.* (2020), cited also in Faiciuc (2020), in which the personality trait of honesty-humility (which might be associated with a postconventional moral reasoning) correlated negatively with the negative perception of lying. This result was explained by the cited authors assuming that “honest individuals tend to approach deception with a more neutral stance. They may circumvent any moral judgment that typically comes with

it and instead perceive deception as an objectively common phenomenon with no intrinsic nor absolute moral value.” (p. 26). Correlatively, it may be that those people preferring the lowest stage of moral reasoning, the one that is based on the norms imposed by an external authority, might have a more rigid/dogmatic, less nuanced, perception regarding hiding the truth, considering that it is unacceptable no matter the context. This explanation is reflected also in the results of the detailed analysis of the relationship between the total score of C2 and MVE score for each item of the SRM-SFO. The total score of C2 correlated negatively with the MVE score for the moral value of **“telling the truth” (item 4)**, as predicted, and, additionally, with the MVE score for the moral value of **“not taking away things that belong to others” (item 8)**, and, weaker, with the MVE score for the moral value of **“children helping their parents” (item 5)**, which are basic moral rules supported by the parental authority. In contrast, the above-mentioned score did not correlate similarly with the scores indicating the preferred stage of moral reasoning for each item of SRM-SFO. It correlated, as predicted, negatively significantly with all the scores of moral reasoning supporting the importance of the moral value of **“keeping promises, if one can, to friends” (item 1)**: the SRMS score, the stage of the “closest” answer, the mean stage of the “close” answers. It also correlated, as predicted, negatively statistically significantly with two of the scores of moral reasoning supporting the importance of the moral value of **“a person (without losing his or her own life) saving the life of a friend” (item 6)**: the SRMS score, and the mean stage of the “close” answers. Total score of C2 correlated, as predicted, negatively, with the SRMS score for **item 7 (“a person saving the life a stranger, without losing his/her own life”)**, and tended to correlate negatively with the stage of the “closest” answer for this item. In comparison with the results regarding the link between the general score of C5 and the preferred moral reasoning stage for the ten moral values investigated with SRM-SFO, the ones obtained regarding the corresponding link in the case of C2 indicate that the general score of C2 is negatively linked more with the level of moral reasoning of those investigated moral values for which the social obligation or control regarding their observance may be perceived to be at a higher level (as it is in the close relationship with friends). In the same time, it correlated positively, unexpectedly and in opposition with the correspondent results obtained in the case of C5, with the preferred level of moral reasoning of some of those moral values for which the social obligation or control regarding their observance may be perceived to be at a lower level: with the stage of the “closest” answer of the moral value for **“parents keeping a promise to their children” (item 3)**, and, as a tendency, with the stage of the “closest” answer of the moral value of **“obeying the law” (item 9)**. It seems also that the general tendency to consider hiding the truth as justified assessed with C2 might be positively associated with the level of moral reasoning for the investigated moral values that imply having trust in the relationship with some kind of authority (of the parents, or of the law), and negatively with the level of moral

reasoning for those moral values that imply the maintenance of trust in interpersonal relationships, especially of the close ones. These positive and negative associations of the general score of C2 with the moral reasoning level for the items of SRM-SFO explain the absence of its expected relationship with the general level of moral reasoning assessed with SRM-SFO. It is notable that no correlation was obtained between any moral reasoning score for the moral value of **“telling the truth” (item 4)** and the total score of C2, which is an unexpected result that occurred also for the correspondent score of C5. Of all the investigated moral values, only the level of moral reasoning for the moral value of **“a person saving the life a stranger, without losing his/her own life”** (a value that synthesizes care and fairness) was negatively linked both with the general tendency to hide the truth as assessed with C5 (in this case only as a tendency), and the general tendency to consider hiding the truth justified, no matter the reason.

Item 31 of C2 (“There is no justification for hiding the truth in any situation, regardless of the context.”), which indicates the explicit global attitude regarding the justification of hiding the truth no matter the conditions in which it may occur, tended to correlate negatively (in the opposite direction than the predicted one) with the MVE score for the moral value of **“parents keeping a promise to their children” (item 3)**, with the MVE score for the moral value of **“a person (without losing his or her own life) saving the life of a friend” (item 6)**, and with the MVE score for the moral value of **“judges sending people who break the law to jail” (item 10)**, and tended to correlate positively (as expected) with the MVE score for the moral value of **“obeying the law” (item 9)**. It also correlated negatively statistically significantly, in the opposite direction than the predicted one, with the stage of the “closest” answer of the moral value of **“keeping promises, if one can, to friends” (item 1)**, and tended to correlate negatively with the SRMS score of that moral value. Another unexpected statistically significant negative correlation was the one between the answer at item 31 and the stage of the “closest” answer for the moral value of **“parents keeping a promise to their children” (item 3)**. Also, the answer at item 31 tended to correlate negatively unexpectedly with the mean stage of the “close” answers for the moral value of **“a person (without losing his or her own life) saving the life of a friend” (item 6)**. In comparison with the corresponding results obtained with the total score of C2, which indicates implicitly, indirectly, the general position regarding the inadmissibility of hiding the truth, the ones obtained with item 31, which requires the explicit position regarding the inadmissibility of hiding the truth, are similar only regarding the relationship between the above-mentioned scores and the level of moral reasoning for the moral value of **“parents keeping a promise to their children” (item 3)**. In both cases, the more hiding the truth was considered unjustified in general (implicitly or explicitly), the lower was the preferred level of moral reasoning for the moral value of **“parents keeping a promise to their children”**. In the same time, for the moral values of **“keeping promises, if one**

can, to friends” (item 1), and of “a person (without losing his or her own life) saving the life of a friend” (item 6), for item 31 the pattern of results was in opposition with the one obtained for the total score of C2 and with the expected one. It seems that an explicit rigid position toward telling/hiding the truth may be linked with a more immature moral argumentation of the moral obligations toward persons with the same or a lower social status than the moral agent, and, in the same time, to a lower importance attributed to them, in the case of the moral value of “parents keeping a promise to their children”, and of “a person (without losing his or her own life) saving the life of a friend” (item 6).

Given the results of the above-mentioned detailed analyses, if they are not purely random ones, it seems that the link of the general position regarding hiding the truth with the importance attributed to the various investigated moral values, as well as with their preferred level/stage of moral reasoning depends on the way this general position regarding hiding the truth is assessed: implicitly, or explicitly, as a self-reported behavior of hiding the truth in the specified conditions (as in C5), or as an attitude toward the behavior of hiding the truth in the specified conditions (as in C2). These results suggest also that the relationship obtained between the general scores of C2 and C5 with the general scores of SRM-SFO regarding moral value evaluation (MVE) and the preferred stage of moral reasoning might be based more on some particular relationships of those C2 and C5 general scores with the MVE and moral reasoning scores computed only for some of the investigated moral values, which seem to be more representative for characterizing one’s moral judgment and behavior in general.

Relationship of the scores for the five levels of reasons of hiding the truth and of the synthetic scores computed for C5 (willingness to hie the truth), and, respectively, for C2 (tendency to consider hiding the truth as justified) with the general and item scores of SRM-SFO that indicate moral reasoning maturity and moral value evaluation

For C5, among the five levels of reasons for hiding the truth, only the first two, representing egocentric reasons for hiding the truth, correlated negatively significantly, as expected, with most of the scores indicating the general level of moral reasoning. The exceptions were the scores computed solely based on the “close” answers at SRM-SFO: the mean of the stage of all “close” answers of SRMS-SFO, which did not correlate with the preference for the second level of the reasons for hiding the truth, and only tended to correlate negatively with the preference for the first level of the reasons for hiding the truth, and the mean of the mean stage of “close” answers at each item of SRMS-SFO, which did not correlate significantly negatively with the preference for the second level of the reasons for hiding the truth. A similar pattern of results was obtained for the synthetic score of the egocentric reasons for hiding the truth, which correlated negatively statistically

significantly only with those scores of moral reasoning that involved in their computation the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO. The mean of the stage of “closest” answers at each item of SRMS-SFO tended to correlate negatively also with the reasons of hiding the truth of level 3. No correlation was obtained between the scores for altruistic reasons for hiding the truth, or those regarding mixed reasons for hiding the truth, and the scores for the general level of moral reasoning of SRM-SFO. MVE score, also, correlated negatively statistically significantly, as expected, with the preference for egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 2, but only tended, very weakly, to correlate with the preference for egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 1, and with the general score for the egocentric reasons for hiding the truth. The preference for the altruistic reasons of hiding the truth or for those with a mixed character did not correlate with the general score regarding the importance attributed to the moral values assessed with SRM-SFO (i.e., MVE). Of the above-mentioned results, the most stable ones, when the relative preference for the reasons for hiding the truth was considered (i.e., ipsatized scores), are the negative link of the preference (the relative one, in this case) for the reasons of hiding the truth of level 2, and respectively, for egocentric reasons of hiding the truth, in general, with the most scores for the general level of moral reasoning of SRM-SFO, i.e., those computed taking into consideration the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO (the only exception was the marginally significant negative correlation between the mean of SRMS for each item of SRMS-SFO, and the general score for egocentric reasons of hiding the truth), and the negative correlation between MVE and the preference (the relative one) for the reasons of hiding the truth of level 2. So, the preference (absolute and relative, as measured with C5) for hiding the truth because other persons have hidden the truth, as a group norm or by virtue of reciprocity, had the most stable negative relationship with the general level of moral reasoning and moral value evaluation as measured with SRM-SFO.

When the planned correlations were computed with the ipsatized scores of C5 that indicate the relative preference for the different types of reasons of hiding the truth, some of the expected positive correlations between the scores for the general level of moral reasoning of SRM-SFO and the relative preference for altruistic reasons of hiding the truth occurred, namely those in which the SRM-SFO scores were computed taking into consideration the “closest” answers. Also, the relative preference for the reasons for hiding the truth of level 4 correlated positively significantly with all the general scores for moral reasoning of SRM-SFO. In this case, too, MVE score correlated positively statistically significantly (as expected) with the relative preference for the altruistic reasons of hiding the truth in general, and, unexpectedly, with the relative preference for the reasons of hiding the truth of level 3 (reasons that indicate the internalization of the truth value, which may explain its positive correlation with MVE, but its weaker level in comparison with the egocentric motivations for hiding the truth). The obtained results indicate that only the relative preference for the altruistic reasons of hiding the truth, particularly

for those of level 4, had the expected positive link with the general level of moral reasoning and moral value evaluation as measured with SRM-SFO.

Comparing the above-mentioned results with the corresponding ones from Faiciuc (2020), the main overlap was the correlation between the global measure of MCT indicating moral competence (and, implicitly, the general level of moral reasoning) with the relative preference for the C5 reasons of hiding the truth of level 4, the only result that occurred also in Faiciuc (2016a), and with the synthetic score of C5 for the egocentric reasons of hiding the truth. Whereas in Faiciuc (2020) there occurred a negative correlation between the index for moral competence of MCT and only the relative preference for the C5 reasons for hiding the truth of level 1, in the present study, some of the global scores indicating the level of moral reasoning assessed with SRM-SFO correlated negatively only with the absolute preference for the C5 egocentric reasons for hiding the truth of level 1. In the present study, the global scores indicating the level of moral reasoning of SRM-SFO correlated negatively in a more stable way with the preference for the C5 egocentric reasons for hiding the truth of level 2 (both with the relative and the absolute one). These results suggest that the relative preference for the different reasons of hiding the truth investigated with C5 has different relationships with the general level of moral reasoning assessed with the two different instruments for the self-reported moral thinking, as, for the egocentric ones, it had a negative relationship, for the pure altruistic ones, it did not have any relationship, and, in the same time, for the reasons of hiding the truth of level 4, in which the altruistic and selfish motivations converge so that to preserve an important relationship with other persons, it had a positive relationship. In the case of the SRM-SFO, the clearest and the more stable results occurred for the scores computed based on the "closest" answers, again. The relative preference for the different reasons of hiding the truth investigated with C5 had also different relationships with the importance attributed in general to the moral values investigated with SRM-SFO (MVE), following a partially similar pattern to the one regarding the level of moral reasoning: for the egocentric ones, especially for the ones of level 2, too, it had the expected negative relationship, and for the altruistic ones, it had the expected positive relationship.

The results presented in the previous two paragraphs are reflected also at the level of the correlations between the preference for the different levels (on the egocentric-altruistic dimension) of the C5 reasons for hiding the truth and the preference for the four stages of moral reasoning of the "closest" answers at SRM-SFO. In this case, too, the investigated link was clearer for the scores of SRM-SFO computed based on the "closest" answers at SRM-SFO. The preference for egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 1, and of level 2 correlated positively statistically significantly, as expected, with the preference for the stage 2 of the immature moral reasoning of the "closest" answers, and negatively statistically significantly with the stage 4 of the mature moral reasoning of those

answers. The preference for egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 2 correlated also negatively statistically significantly, as expected, with the preference for the stage 3 of the mature moral reasoning of the “closest” answers. The expected positive correlations between the preference for the egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 1, and of level 2 with the preference for the stage 1 of the immature moral reasoning of the “closest” answers occurred only as a tendency, as well as the expected positive correlation between the preference for egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 3 and the preference for the stage 2 of the immature moral reasoning of the “closest” answers. The general score for the egocentric reasons of hiding the truth correlated also positively statistically significantly, as expected, with the preference for the stage 2 of the immature moral reasoning of the “closest” answers, and negatively significantly with the stage 4 of the mature moral reasoning of those answers. The preference for the egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 3 correlated negatively statistically significantly, as expected, with the preference for the “closest” answers of stage 4 at SRM-SFO. No statistically significant correlation was obtained between the computed scores of C5 for the altruistic reasons of hiding the truth and the scores for the preferred stage of the closest answers at SRM-SFO, as in the case presented in the previous two paragraphs. Only a slight tendency occurred for the expected positive correlation between the preference for the reasons for hiding the truth of level 4 and the preference for the stage 3 of the mature moral reasoning of the “closest” answers. The score of the preference for the mixed reasons of hiding the truth (in which the altruistic and egocentric reasons of hiding the truth are in competition) tended also to correlate negatively with preference for the moral reasoning of stage 4 of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO. As expected, the preference for egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 1, and of level 2, as well as the general score for the egocentric reasons of hiding the truth correlated negatively statistically significantly with the synthetic score of SRM-SFO indicating the preference for the mature stages of moral reasoning, as a percentage of occurrence of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO of stage 3 and 4 for moral reasoning. The expected positive correlations between the scores of C5 for the altruistic reasons of hiding the truth and the preference for the mature stages of moral reasoning, as a percentage of occurrence of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO of stage 3 and 4, did not occur.

When the link of the different levels (on the egocentric-altruistic dimension) of reasons for hiding the truth of C5 with the different scores indicating the preference for the four stages of moral reasoning of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO was investigated with the corresponding ipsatized scores of C5, the results that were the most stable in comparison with the results presented in the previous paragraph were the ones referring to the statistically significant expected negative correlations of the preference (a relative one in this case) for the reasons of hiding the truth of level 2, and of the general preference (a relative one) for egocentric

reasons for hiding the truth with the preference for moral reasoning of level 4, and with the percentage of chosen “closest” answers with a mature level of reasoning (stage 3 and 4). With ipsatized scores for C5, new expected correlations occurred: the statistically significant negative correlation between the preference (a relative one) for reasons of hiding the truth of level 1 and the preference for “closest” answers with a moral reasoning of stage 3, the statistically significant positive correlation of the preference (a relative one) for reasons of hiding the truth of level 2, as well as of the general relative preference for the egocentric reasons of hiding the truth with the preference for the “closest” answers with a moral reasoning of stage 1 (the corresponding result in the previous paragraph was only a tendency toward such an association), the statistically significant negative correlation of the preference (a relative one) for reasons of hiding the truth of level 4 with the preference for “closest” answers with a moral reasoning of stage 1, as well as the statistically significant positive correlation with the percentage of the “closest” answers of stage 3 and 4 at SRM-SFO, the negative statistically significant correlation of the general relative preference for altruistic reasons of hiding the truth with the preference for the “closest” answers with a moral reasoning of stage 1, and the statistically significant positive correlation for the general relative preference for altruistic reasons of hiding the truth with the preference for “closest” answers with a moral reasoning of stage 4, as well as with the percentage of the chosen “closest” answers with a mature level of reasoning. Whereas the expected positive correlation of the preference for the “closest” answers with a moral reasoning of stage 2 with the preference for reasons of hiding the truth of level 2 was statistically significant (as presented above), its positive correlation with the relative preference for reasons of hiding the truth of level 2 occurred only as a tendency. The positive correlation of the preference for “closest” answers at SRM-SFO with a moral reasoning of stage 3 with the relative preference for reasons of hiding the truth of level 4 occurred only as a tendency, as it was the case for the corresponding correlation presented above for the absolute preference for reasons of hiding the truth of level 4.

In the case of the link between the different levels (on the egocentric-altruistic dimension) of reasons for hiding the truth of C5 and SRM-SFO scores indicating the preference for the four stages of moral reasoning of the “close” answers at SRM-SFO, only the following expected correlations were obtained: the preference for egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 1, and of level 2, as well as the general score for the egocentric reasons for hiding the truth of C5 correlated negatively significantly with the preference for the stage 4 of moral reasoning of the “close” answers at SRM-SFO. They correspond to the similar ones obtained when in the computed correlations were used the SRM-SFO scores indicating the preference for the four stages of moral reasoning of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO. When the above-mentioned link was investigated using the ipsatized scores for C5, the above-mentioned statistically significant correlations

obtained with absolute scores of C5 occurred only in the case of the expected negative correlation between the relative preference for egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of C5 and the preference for the stage 4 of moral reasoning of the “close” answers at SRM-SFO. In this case, the preference (a relative one) for egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 1, and of level 2 only tended to correlate negatively with the preference for the stage 4 of moral reasoning of the “close” answers at SRM-SFO, and, supplementary, tended to correlate negatively with the preference for the stage 3 of moral reasoning of the “close” answers at SRM-SFO. In the same time, the preference (a relative one) for egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 1, and of level 2 correlated negatively significantly, as predicted, with the percentage of the answers with a mature moral reasoning (of stage 3 and 4). Unexpectedly, the preference (a relative one) for egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 3 correlated positively statistically significantly with the preference for the stage 3 of moral reasoning of the “close” answers at SRM-SFO, and with the percentage of the answers with a mature moral reasoning (of stage 3 and 4). It is a result that may be explained based on the meaning of these reasons of hiding the truth, which imply the internalization of the moral value of truth, even though it may be surpassed by egocentric motivations. The general score indicating the relative preference for egocentric reasons of hiding the truth correlated negatively statistically significantly with the preference for the stage 3, and stage 4 of moral reasoning of the “close” answers at SRM-SFO, and with the percentage of the answers with a mature moral reasoning (of stage 3 and 4). The relative preference for altruistic reasons of hiding the truth only tended to correlate positively with the preference for the stage 4 of moral reasoning of the “close” answers at SRM-SFO. Also, the relative preference for the reasons of hiding the truth of level 4 only tended to correlate negatively with the preference for the stage 1 of moral reasoning of the “close” answers at SRM-SFO. In the discussed case, the relative preference for the mixed reasons of hiding the truth (in which the altruistic and egocentric reasons are in competition) correlated positively with the preference for the stage 3 of moral reasoning of the “close” answers at SRM-SFO, and with the percentage of the answers with a mature moral reasoning (of stage 3 and 4).

Again, the pattern of correlations of the relative and, respectively, absolute preference for different levels of the C5 reasons of hiding the truth with the preference for the four stages of moral reasoning assessed with SRM-SFO was closer to the expected one in the case of the corresponding scores computed based on the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO, in comparison with the case in which the “close” answers were used, but the patterns of correlations were similar in the two cases. The expected pattern of correlations was supported by data in a high proportion in the case of the scores computed based on the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO, especially for the correlations computed with the relative and absolute

preference for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 2, and, in general, for the correlations computed with the relative preference for the five types of C5 reasons of hiding the truth (when the influence of some possible responses biases might have been partially eliminated). In this case, the overlap with the corresponding data obtained in Faiciuc (2020) and Faiciuc (2016a)¹ was high, too. Nevertheless, the pattern of correlations of these type that were computed using SRM-SFO was, again, closer to the expected pattern than the one of the correlations computed using MCT. In general, the greatest overlap with the expected results in all the three studies was the one regarding the predicted positive association of the (absolute or relative) preference for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of lower levels with the preference for the lower levels/stages of moral reasoning. In the present study, the expected negative correlation between the (absolute or relative) preference for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth and the preference for the higher levels/stages of moral reasoning, as well as the expected positive correlation between the (absolute or relative) preference for the C5 altruistic reasons of hiding the truth and the preference for the higher levels/stages of moral reasoning were clearer.

For C2, only the preference for the egocentric reasons for hiding the truth of level 2 had some of the expected correlations with the general scores of SRM-SFO: it correlated negatively statistically significantly with all of them, with the exception of its correlations with the mean of the stage of “closest” answers at each item of SRM-SFO. Unexpectedly, the preference for the egocentric reasons for hiding the truth of level 1 correlated statistically significantly negatively (not positively, as expected) with the preference for the moral reasoning of the stage 1 of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO, and also tended to correlate unexpectedly positively with the preference for the moral reasoning of the stage 3 of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO, and with the percentage of stage 3 and 4 of

¹ In Faiciuc (2016a), the score for the egocentric and, respectively, altruistic reasons of hiding the truth were computed differently than in Faiciuc (2020) and in the present study (i.e., in the same way they were computed for C2 here). Nevertheless, the results are similar to the ones obtained on the data from Faiciuc (2016a) if, in the corresponding correlations, those scores are computed in the same way as in Faiciuc (2020) and here. So, the score for the preference for the egocentric reasons of hiding the truth correlated positively statistically significantly (in Faiciuc 2016a, only tended to correlate positively) with the preference for the moral reasoning of stage 1, as measured with MCT ($\rho = .283, p = .042, N = 38$), whereas the score for the preference for the altruistic reasons of hiding the truth correlated positively statistically significantly (in Faiciuc 2016a, only tended to correlate positively) with the preference for the mature moral reasoning of stage 4, as measured with MCT ($\rho = .263, p = .046, N = 42$), but also tended to correlate positively with the preference for the MCT moral reasoning of stage 3 ($\rho = .238, p = .065, N = 41$). As in the data presented in Faiciuc (2016a), the relative preference for the moral reasoning of stage 2 correlated positively with the relative preference for the egocentric reasons of hiding the truth ($\rho = .321, p = .025, N = 38$), but also tended to correlate positively (in Faiciuc, 2016a, tended to correlate negatively) with the relative preference for the altruistic reasons of hiding the truth ($\rho = .238, p = .075, N = 38$).

“closest” answers. The preference for the egocentric reasons for hiding the truth of level 2, instead, correlated, as expected, positively statistically significantly with the preference for the moral reasoning of the stage 1, and stage 2 of the “close” answers at SRM-SFO, and tended, as expected, to correlate negatively with the preference for the moral reasoning of the stage 4 of the of the “closest”, and “close” answers at SRM-SFO. The preference for the reasons for hiding the truth of level 4 correlated statistically significantly positively with the preference for the moral reasoning of the stage 3 of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO, and tended, as expected, to correlate negatively with the preference for the moral reasoning of the stage 1 of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO, but, unexpectedly, it also tended to correlate positively with the preference for the moral reasoning of the stage 2 of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO. Also, unexpectedly, it correlated statistically significantly negatively with the preference for the moral reasoning of the stage 4 of the “close” answers at SRM-SFO. The preference for the reasons for hiding the truth of level 5 only tended to correlate positively with the preference for the mature moral reasoning of the stage 3 of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO. The general score for the preference for altruistic reasons of hiding the truth at C2 correlated, as expected, positively statistically significantly with the preference for the mature moral reasoning of the stage 3 of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO, and tended to correlate negatively with the preference for the immature moral reasoning of the stage 1 of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO.

The general score for moral value evaluation of SRM-SFO (MVE) correlated or tended (in two cases, i.e. the preference for the reasons for hiding the truth of level 2, and of level 3) to correlate negatively with the preference for all the different levels (on the egocentric-altruistic dimension) of reasons for hiding the truth of C2.

The above-mentioned results that involve the reasons of hiding the truth of level 2 should be considered with caution, as the corresponding C2 scale had a very low internal consistency.

Comparing the pattern of correlations of the preference for the different levels of reasons of hiding the truth assessed with C2 with the general scores computed for SRM-SFO, and with the scores for the preference for the four moral reasoning stages assessed with SRM-SFO with the corresponding pattern of correlations computed with the preference for the different levels of reasons of hiding the truth assessed with C5, the most stable results were the expected negative relationships of the preference for the egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 2 with the general scores of SRM-SFO assessing the level of moral reasoning, and, respectively, with the preference for the four stages of moral reasoning assessed with SRM-SFO. The unexpected results occurring in the C2 case may be linked with the way C2 items were formulated, suggesting a different meaning than the one of the C5 items, as discussed above. This particular meaning is more obvious reflected by the negative correlations of the general score for

moral value evaluation of SRM-SFO (MVE) with the preference for all the different levels (on the egocentric-altruistic dimension) of reasons for hiding the truth of C2, a result that is different than the one obtained for the corresponding correlations in the C5 case. Some of the above-mentioned types of unexpected results occurred also in Faiciuc (2016a), as the positive correlation of the preference for the C2 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 1 with the preference for the mature stages of moral reasoning (that were assessed with MCT), as well as with the moral competence index (which is associated with the general level of moral reasoning), which were explained based on the ambiguous meaning of some of the C2 items of level 1.

The SRMS score regarding the level of moral reasoning for the moral value of **“truth telling”** (item 4) of SRM-SFO correlated positively statistically significantly, as expected, only with the general absolute score for the C5 altruistic reasons of hiding the truth, and with the absolute preference for the C5 reasons of hiding the truth of level 4, and only tended to correlate positively with the absolute preference for the C5 reasons of hiding the truth of level 5. When using the ipsatized scores for C5, instead, it correlated negatively statistically significantly, as predicted, also with the relative preference for the reasons of hiding the truth of level 1, and of level 2, positively, as predicted, with the relative preference for the reasons of hiding the truth of level 4, and tended to correlate positively with the relative preference for the reasons of hiding the truth of level 5, and the relative preference for the altruistic reasons of hiding the truth. The moral reasoning stage of the “closest” answer for the moral value of **“truth telling”** of SRM-SFO also correlated positively statistically significantly, as expected, with the absolute preference for the C5 reasons of hiding the truth of level 4, and only tended to correlate positively with the absolute preference for the reasons of hiding the truth of level 5, but also tended to correlate positively with the absolute preference for the altruistic reasons of hiding the truth. When using the ipsatized scores for C5, it correlated also statistically significantly negatively, as predicted, with the relative preference for the reasons of hiding the truth of level 1, and only tended to correlate positively with the relative preference for the reasons of hiding the truth of level 4, and of level 5. The mean moral reasoning stage of the “close” answers for the moral value of **“truth telling”** of SRM-SFO only tended to correlate positively with the absolute preference for the C5 reasons of hiding the truth of level 4. When using the ipsatized scores for C5, it correlated statistically significantly, as expected, negatively with the relative preference for the reasons of hiding the truth of level 2, and positively with the relative preference for the reasons of hiding the truth of level 4. Finally, the importance of the moral value of **“telling the truth”** (item 4), as expected, correlated statistically significantly positively with the relative preference for the altruistic reasons for hiding the truth from C5, and only tended to correlate negatively with the absolute preference for egocentric reasons for hiding the truth of level 1, and of level 2.

So, for C5, it seems that the preferred level for the moral reasoning in justifying the moral value of telling the truth, especially the one assessed with scores based on the “closest” answers at the SRM-SFO, correlated partially as expected with the preference for the different levels of reasons of hiding the truth, mainly regarding its negative link with the relative preference for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth, and its positive link with the general score for the C5 altruistic reasons of hiding the truth, particularly with the absolute and relative preference for the C5 reasons of hiding the truth of level 4 (a result that supports the special status of this kind of reasons of hiding the truth, which occurred constantly in all the three studies, the present one, and the one from 2020 and 2016). The evaluation of the importance of truth telling was mainly positively linked (the expected direction of the relationship) with the general score for the C5 altruistic reasons of hiding the truth. So, the position regarding telling the truth was mainly linked with the C5 altruistic reasons of hiding the truth. These results for C5 were not obtained in the case of C2, suggesting again that the format of the C2 items gives them a different meaning than the one of the C5 items, although their content may seem similar.

As noted above, for C2, none of the scores that indicate the preferred level of moral reasoning for the moral value of **“truth telling” (item 4)** correlated significantly with the scores for the different types of reasons for hiding the truth of C2. The score that indicates the attributed importance to the moral value of **“truth telling” (item 4)** correlated, instead, significantly negatively with all of the scores of C2, with the exception of the preference for the egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 2, with which only tended to correlate negatively. This result indicates one more time that C2 may assess less the respondent’s personal position regarding the truth telling/hiding, and more her/his perception of the way truth telling is considered as a community norm.

Unexpectedly, the C5 scores for the different levels (on the egocentric-altruistic dimension) of reasons for hiding the truth of C5 correlated sometimes more with the level of moral reasoning and with the importance of other moral values assessed with SRM-SFO than with the ones regarding the truth telling **“truth telling” (item 4)**. The absolute preference for the egocentric reasons for hiding the truth of level 1, and of level 2 correlated negatively statistically significantly with the value attributed to **“saving the life of a friend (without losing his or her own life)” (item 6)**. The importance of the moral value of **“saving the life of a friend (without losing his or her own life)” (item 6)** correlated statistically significantly negatively also with the relative preference for egocentric reasons for hiding the truth of level 1, and of level 2, and positively with the relative preference for altruistic reasons of hiding the truth. The absolute preference for egocentric reasons for hiding the truth of level 2 correlated negatively statistically significantly with the value attributed to **“saving the life of a stranger (without losing his or her own life)” (item 7)**. The importance of the

moral value of **“saving the life of a stranger (without losing his or her own life)” (item 7)** correlated statistically significantly negatively with the relative preference for egocentric reasons for hiding the truth of level 2, too, and with the relative preference for egocentric reasons of hiding the truth, and positively with the relative preference for altruistic reasons of hiding the truth. The above-mentioned correlations may be linked with the “saving” meaning of the items 6 and 7 of SRM-SFO, which may be more linked with the egocentric/altruistic motivations than the meaning of the truth telling item. The preference for the egocentric reasons for hiding the truth of level 1 correlated statistically significantly unexpectedly positively with the value attributed to **“judges sending people who break the law to jail” (item 10)**. This result may be understood by taking into consideration that the preference for the egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 1 may be linked with a kind of moral orientation for which the external authority figures (judges, in this case) are important as a source of moral norms. The importance of the moral value of **“keeping promises, if one can, to friends” (item 1)** and the importance of the moral value of **“keeping promises, if you can, to a person you hardly know” (item 2)** correlated statistically significantly negatively with the relative preference for egocentric reasons for hiding the truth, and statistically significantly positively with the relative preference for altruistic reasons for hiding. It may be that keeping promises is more important for maintaining trust in interpersonal relationship than simply telling the truth in any situation. The importance of the moral value of **“parents keeping promises, if they can, to their children” (item 3)** correlated statistically significantly negatively with the relative preference for egocentric reasons for hiding the truth of level 2, and positively with the relative preference for the reasons for hiding the truth of level 3 ($\rho = .435$, $p = .003$, $N = 39$), and with the relative preference for mixed reasons of hiding the truth. The importance of the moral value of **“children helping their parents” (item 5)** correlated statistically significantly positively with the relative preference for the reasons for hiding the truth of level 3, and negatively with the relative preference for egocentric reasons of hiding the truth. The positive associations of the importance attributed to the moral values of the items 3 and, respectively, 5 of SRM-SFO with the relative preference for the C5 reasons of hiding the truth of level 3 may be linked with a deficient internalization of the moral values, which is based mainly on preserving trust in family relationships, a kind of morality that prevails in childhood. The importance of the moral value of **“not taking things that belong to other people” (item 8)** correlated statistically significantly positively with the relative preference for altruistic reasons of hiding the truth. These results indicate that the attitude toward almost all the moral values investigated with SRM-SFO (the only exceptions were the moral values of **“obeying the law”** and **“judges sending people who break the law to jail”**) were linked negatively with the relative preference for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth or positively with the

relative preference for the C5 altruistic reasons of hiding the truth, *i.e.* with the reasons for the transgression of a different moral value, as it is truth telling.

The pattern of correlations of the C5 scores for the different levels (on the egocentric-altruistic dimension) of reasons for hiding the truth of C5 with the scores indicating the level of moral reasoning for the other moral values than the truth telling one also indicated that the reasons for hiding the truth can have a stronger link with the moral reasoning regarding moral values that are not directly linked with truth telling. In the case of the moral value of **“keeping promises, if one can, to friends” (item 1)**, which is a moral value with a meaning indirectly linked with the truth telling, its SRMS score correlated negatively (in the expected direction) with the preference for the egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of C5: statistically significantly with the preference for those of level 2, and of level 3, or as a tendency with those of level 1, and with the synthetic score of the mixed reasons of hiding the truth (in which the altruistic reasons are in competition with the egocentric ones). It did not correlate with the relative preference for the egocentric reasons of hiding the truth, in general, or of any level. It also did not correlate with the preference for altruistic reasons for hiding the truth, but only with the relative preference for them, in which case the expected statistically significant positive correlation was obtained. It correlated negatively statistically significantly with almost all C2 scores for the reasons of hiding the truth, with the exception of the preference for the reasons of hiding the truth of level 4, for which the negative correlation was only marginally significant. In comparison, the stage of the “closest” answer for the above-mentioned moral value correlated negatively statistically significantly only with the preference and the relative preference for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 2, and tended to correlate negatively, unexpectedly, with the preference for the reasons of hiding the truth of level 4. It did not correlate with the preference or relative preference for the C5 altruistic reasons of hiding the truth. In the case of C2, the stage of the “closest” answer for the moral value of **“keeping promises, if one can, to friends” (item 1)** correlated negatively statistically significantly with almost all C2 scores for the reasons of hiding the truth, with the exception of the preference for the reasons of hiding the truth of level 1, for which the negative correlation was only marginally significant, and of the preference for the reasons of hiding the truth of level 2, with which the negative correlation was not even close to the statistical significance threshold. The mean moral reasoning stage of the “close” answers of the discussed moral value correlated negatively with the preference for egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of C5: statistically significantly with the preference for those of level 1, and of level 3, or as a tendency with relative preference for those of level 3, and with the synthetic score of the mixed reasons of hiding the truth (in which the altruistic reasons are in competition with the egocentric ones). It did not correlate with the preference or relative preference for the C5 altruistic reasons of hiding the truth. It correlated negatively statistically significantly with almost all scores of C2

for the reasons of hiding the truth, with the exception of the preference for the altruistic reasons of hiding the truth, for which the negative correlation was only marginally significant, and with the preference for the reasons of hiding the truth of level 4, with which the negative correlation was not even close to the statistical significance threshold.

The moral value of **“keeping promises, if you can, to a person you hardly know” (item 2)**, which is also a moral value with a meaning indirectly linked with the truth telling, had a similar pattern of correlation with the C5 egocentric scores for the reasons of hiding the truth as the one obtained for the item 1 of SRM-SFO, described in the previous paragraph. Its SRMS score correlated also negatively (in the expected direction) with the preference for egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of C5: statistically significantly with the preference for those of level 1 (this time), and of level 3, or as a tendency with those of level 2, but it tended to correlate negatively also with all the synthetic scores of C5. It did not correlate with the relative preference for the reasons of hiding the truth, in general, or of any level. For C2, instead, in opposition with the previous case, it did not correlate with the C2 reasons of hiding the truth, in general, or of any level. The stage of the “closest” answer for the above-mentioned moral value correlated negatively statistically significantly with the preference for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 1, and of level 2, but also unexpectedly, tended to correlate negatively with the preference for the altruistic reasons of hiding the truth of level 5, and statistically significantly negatively both with the synthetic C5 scores for egocentric, and for altruistic reasons of hiding the truth, and tended to correlate also negatively with the synthetic score for the mixed reasons of hiding the truth (in which the altruistic reasons are in competition with the egocentric ones). It did not correlate with the relative preference for the C5 reasons of hiding the truth, in general, or of any level. For C2, it did not correlate with the C2 reasons of hiding the truth, in general, or of any level, either. The mean moral reasoning stage of the “close” answers of the discussed moral value tended slightly to correlate negatively with the preference for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 1, of level 2, and of level 3, and also with the preference for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 4, and with the synthetic score of the mixed reasons of hiding the truth (in which the altruistic reasons are in competition with egocentric ones). Unexpectedly, it correlated negatively statistically significantly with the synthetic C5 score for the altruistic reasons of hiding the truth. It did not correlate instead with the relative preference for the C5 altruistic reasons of hiding the truth. These results suggest that the higher the level of moral reasoning for supporting this moral value that implies preservation of the trust in relationships with strangers, the lower is the willingness to hide the truth, no matter the reason. In comparison, the results presented in the previous paragraph, suggest that the higher the level of moral reasoning for supporting this moral value that implies preservation of the trust in relationships with friends, the lower is the willingness to

hide the truth only for the egocentric or mixed reasons of hiding the truth. The preference for the different types of C2 reasons for which hiding the truth is considered justified seem to be not linked with the level of moral reasoning for supporting the moral value that implies preservation of the trust in relationship with strangers. It was negatively linked instead with the level of moral reasoning for supporting the moral value that implies preservation of the trust in relationships with friends.

For the last moral value linked indirectly with the value of telling the truth, i.e. **“parents keeping promises, if they can, to their children” (item 3)**, SRMS score correlated also negatively (in the expected direction) with the preference for egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of C5: statistically significantly with the preference for those of level 1, and, as a tendency with the preference for those of level 3, and correlated statistically significantly negatively with the synthetic score for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth. It did not correlate with the relative preference for the C5 reasons of hiding the truth, in general, or of any level. In the case of C2, it correlated positively (in the expected direction) statistically significantly only with the preference for the C2 altruistic reasons of hiding the truth of level 5, and tended to correlate positively with the synthetic score for the C2 altruistic reasons of hiding the truth. The stage of the “closest” answer for the above-mentioned moral value correlated statistically significantly negatively (in the expected direction) with the preference for the egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of C5: of level 1, of level 2, and of level 3, and also with the synthetic scores for preference for the C5 egocentric and mixed reasons of hiding the truth (in which the altruistic reasons are in competition with the egocentric ones). For the C5 ipsatized scores, it correlated statistically significantly positively only with the synthetic score for the relative preference for the C5 altruistic reasons of hiding the truth. It correlated also statistically significantly positively only with the synthetic score for the C2 altruistic reasons of hiding the truth, and with the preference for the C2 altruistic reasons of hiding the truth of level 5. But it also tended to correlate positively with the preference for the C2 altruistic reasons of hiding the truth of level 4, and, unexpectedly, with the preference for the C2 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 1. The mean moral reasoning stage of the “close” answers of the discussed moral value, unexpectedly, correlated positively statistically significantly with the preference and the relative preference for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 2, but also with the preference and the relative preference for the C5 reasons of hiding the truth of level 4. In the same time, it tended to correlate negatively, as expected, with the relative preference for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 1, and tended, unexpectedly, to correlate negatively with the relative preference for the C5 altruistic reasons of hiding the truth (as a synthetic score). For C2, it only tended to correlate positively, as expected, with the preference for the C2 altruistic reasons of hiding the truth of level 5. The pattern of the relationships of the level of the moral

reasoning for this value that implies preservation of the trust in relationships with children (or maybe persons with social status that is lower in the power hierarchy) with the different levels of the C5 reasons for hiding the truth was similar with the corresponding one for the preferred moral reasoning stage for the value that implies preservation of the trust in relationships with friends, the notable difference being that, in this case, also a slight positive relationship occurred between the level of moral reasoning for the value discussed in this paragraph and the synthetic score for the relative preference for the C5 altruistic reasons of hiding the truth. For C2, in comparison with the cases of the two previously discussed moral values that imply preservation of the trust in relationships with friends or, respectively, strangers, the level of moral reasoning for this value that implies preservation of the trust in relationships with children was positively linked with the C2 altruistic reasons of hiding the truth, mainly of the highest level (level 5).

For the moral value of **“children helping their parents” (item 5)**, its SRMS score correlated also statistically significantly negatively (in the expected direction) with the preference and relative preference for C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 2, and, tended to correlate negatively with the synthetic score for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth, and with the relative preference for this type of reasons of hiding the truth. For C2, it did not correlate with the C2 reasons of hiding the truth, in general, or of any level. The stage of the “closest” answer for this moral value only tended to correlate negatively with the preference and relative preference for C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 2, and with the relative preference for the mixed reasons of hiding the truth (in which the altruistic reasons are in competition with the egocentric ones). For C2, it also tended to correlate negatively with the preference for the C2 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 2. The mean moral reasoning stage of the “close” answers of the discussed moral value correlated negatively with the preference and relative preference for C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 1 (as a tendency), and of level 2 (statistically significant), as well as with the synthetic score for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth (statistically significant). It tended, unexpectedly, to correlate also positively with the relative preference for the egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 3, and with the relative preference for the mixed reasons of hiding the truth (as a synthetic score). As expected, it correlated positively statistically significantly with the relative preference for the altruistic reasons of hiding the truth (as a synthetic score). For C2, it did not correlate with the C2 reasons of hiding the truth, in general, or of any level. So, in this case, the most stable results are the negative link of the level of moral reasoning supporting the discussed value with the preference or relative preference for the reasons of hiding of truth of level 2, and with the synthetic score for the mixed reasons of hiding the truth.

The SRMS score for the moral value of **“saving the life of a friend (without losing his or her own life)” (item 6)** correlated negatively statistically

significantly only with the relative preference for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 1, and with the relative preference for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth (as a synthetic score), and only tended to correlate negatively with the preference for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 1. It did not correlate with the preference or relative preference for the C5 altruistic reasons of hiding the truth. For C2, instead, it correlated, unexpectedly, negatively and statistically significantly with the preference for the C2 reasons of hiding the truth of level 4, and of level 5, as well as with the preference for the altruistic reasons of hiding the truth (as a synthetic score). In the same time, in this case, too, it tended to correlate negatively with the preference for the C2 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 1. The stage of the “closest” answer for this moral value correlated, too, negatively, statistically significantly this time, with the preference and the relative preference for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 1, but it tended to correlate negatively also with the preference and the relative preference for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 2. It correlated negatively statistically significantly with the relative preference for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth, whereas with the preference for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth it only tended to correlate negatively. Additionally, it tended to correlate positively with the relative preference for the C5 altruistic reasons of hiding the truth, and with the relative preference for the C5 reasons of hiding the truth of level 4. For C2, instead, it tended to correlate negatively with the preference for the C2 altruistic reasons of hiding the truth, and with the preference for the C2 reasons of hiding the truth of level 4. The mean moral reasoning stage of the “close” answers of this moral value only tended to correlate negatively with the relative preference for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 1. For C2, instead, this moral reasoning score correlated negatively statistically significantly with the preference for almost all the different levels of reasons of hiding the truth, and with the two synthetic scores, with the exception of the preference for the C2 reasons of hiding the truth of level 2, with which only tended to correlate negatively. So, for this value, the most stable result in the case of C5 was the negative link of its level of moral reasoning with the preference or relative preference for the reasons of hiding of truth of level 1, and, in the case of C2, the negative link of its level of moral reasoning with almost all the different levels of reasons of hiding the truth, especially with the preference for the altruistic reasons of hiding the truth.

In the case of the moral value of **“saving the life of a stranger (without losing his or her own life)” (item 7)**, its SRMS score correlated negatively both with the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth: statistically significantly with preference for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 1, and, as a tendency, with the preference for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 3, and with the preference for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth (as

a synthetic score), and, unexpectedly, statistically significantly, with the preference, and the relative preference for the C5 altruistic reasons of hiding the truth (as a synthetic score), as well as with the C5 reasons of hiding the truth of level 5, as a tendency. For C2, a similar pattern of results was obtained, as the discussed score correlated negatively with the preference for the C2 reasons of hiding the truth of level 1 (as a tendency), of level 3 (as a tendency), of level 5 (statistically significant), and with the preference for the C2 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth (as a tendency), and for the C2 altruistic reasons of hiding the truth (statistically significant). The moral reasoning stage of the “closest” answer of this moral value correlated negatively statistically significantly with almost all C5 scores indicating the preference for the different levels of reasons of hiding the truth and the computed synthetic scores, with the exception of the preference for the C5 reasons of hiding the truth of level 4. With ipsatized scores, instead, it correlated negatively only with the C5 altruistic reasons of hiding the truth of level 5, and tended to correlate positively with the C5 reasons of hiding the truth of level 4. The preference for the C2 altruistic reasons of hiding the truth of level 5 also correlated negatively statistically significantly with the discussed SRM-SFO score, which also tended to correlate negatively with the preference for the reasons of hiding the truth of level 3. The mean moral reasoning stage of the “close” answers of this moral value, instead, correlated unexpectedly positively with the preference (as a tendency) and with the relative preference (statistically significant) for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 2, and tended to correlate positively with the relative preference for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth, and negatively with relative preference for the C5 altruistic reasons of hiding the truth (a pattern of results in opposition with the expected one). For C2 instead, it did not correlate with the C2 reasons of hiding the truth, in general, or of any level. The most stable result for this value was the unexpected negative link between its level of moral reasoning and preference (absolute or relative) for the altruistic reasons of hiding the truth, especially the ones of level 5. It is a result more similar with the one described above for the moral value of keeping promises toward strangers. The negative link between its level of moral reasoning and the preference for the egocentric reasons of hiding the truth, especially those of level 1, was more unstable and weaker than in the case discussed in the previous paragraph, for the moral value of saving the life of a friend, which is similar in content with the moral value of saving the life of a stranger.

For the moral value of **“not taking things that belong to other people” (item 8)**, a value that can be indirectly linked with the moral value of telling the truth, the SRMS score correlated statistically significantly negatively with the preference for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 1, of level 2, and of level 3, as well as with the preference for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth, and with the preference for the mixed reasons of hiding the truth (as synthetic scores). With ipsatized scores, it correlated negatively statistically

significantly only with the relative preference for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 2, and with the relative preference for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth. Additionally, it correlated positively statistically significantly, as expected, with the relative preference for the C5 altruistic reasons of hiding the truth, and tended to correlate positively with the relative preference for the C5 reasons of hiding the truth of level 4. For C2 instead, it did not correlate with the C2 reasons of hiding the truth, in general, or of any level. The moral reasoning stage of the “closest” answer of the discussed moral value had a similar pattern of correlations with the preference for the C5 reasons of hiding the truth of different levels, and with the C5 synthetic scores on the egocentric-altruistic dimension as its SRMS score. The only difference was the occurrence of a statistically significant unexpected negative correlation between this SRM-SFO score and the preference for the C5 altruistic reasons of hiding the truth. With ipsatized scores, the results were very similar to the corresponding ones obtained with the SRMS score. It correlated, too, negatively statistically significantly only with the relative preference for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 2, and with the relative preference for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth. Additionally, it correlated also positively statistically significantly, as expected, with the relative preference for the C5 altruistic reasons of hiding the truth, but also, in this case, with the relative preference for the C5 reasons of hiding the truth of level 4. For C2 instead, it did not correlate, too, with the C2 reasons of hiding the truth, in general, or of any level. The mean moral reasoning stage of the “close” answers of this moral value correlated statistically significantly negatively, as expected, only with the preference, and the relative preference for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 2. The same result was obtained with the C2 scores, as it correlated statistically significantly negatively, as expected, only with the preference and the relative preference for the C2 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 2. The most stable result in the case of this value was the negative link of its level of moral reasoning with the absolute and relative preference for the egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 2 (predominantly of C5), but the negative link of its level of moral reasoning with the absolute and relative preference for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth occurred also when the level of moral reasoning was assessed with the SRMS score and the stage of the “closest” answer. The preference for the altruistic reasons of hiding the truth had a reversed relationship with the level of moral reasoning for the discussed moral value as assessed with the stage of the “closest” answer in comparison with the relationship between the relative preference for the altruistic reasons of hiding the truth and the level of moral reasoning for the discussed moral value as assessed with the stage of the “closest” answer or with the SRMS score.

In the case of the moral value of **“obeying the law” (item 9)**, its SRMS score only tended to correlate negatively with the preference, and the relative preference for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 2, and correlated positively statistically significantly with the relative preference for the C5 reasons of hiding the truth of level 4. For C2, it correlated positively statistically significantly with the preference for the C2 altruistic reasons of hiding the truth of level 5, and tended to correlate positively with the preference for the C2 altruistic reasons of hiding the truth (as a synthetic score), but it also tended to correlate positively, unexpectedly, with the preference for the C2 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 1. The moral reasoning stage of the “closest” answer for this moral value correlated also positively with the preference (as a tendency), and with the relative preference (statistically significantly) for the C5 reasons of hiding the truth of level 4. For C2, it only tended to correlated positively with the preference for the C2 reasons of hiding the truth of level 4, but it correlated instead positively statistically significantly with the preference for the C2 reasons of hiding the truth of level 5, and, unexpectedly with the preference for the C2 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 1, and of level 3. It also tended to correlate positively with the preference for the C2 altruistic reasons of hiding the truth. The mean moral reasoning stage of the “close” answers of this moral value correlated negatively with the preference for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 1 (statistically significantly), of level 2 (statistically significantly), and of level 3 (as a tendency), and also with the preference for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth (statistically significantly). With ipsatized scores, it correlated negatively statistically significantly only with the relative preference for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 2. It correlated also positively statistically significantly with the relative preference for the C5 reasons of hiding the truth of level 4. For C2, it correlated also negatively statistically significantly with the preference for the C2 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 2, and tended to correlate positively with the preference for the C2 reasons of hiding the truth of level 5. So, the most stable result for this moral value is the positive link of its level of moral reasoning with the relative preference for the C5 reasons of hiding the truth of level 4. For C2, instead, the most stable result was the positive link of the level of moral reasoning of the discussed value with the preference for the C5 reasons of hiding the truth of level 5.

Finally, in the case of the moral value of **“judges sending people who break the law to jail” (item 10)**, its SRMS score did not correlate with the C5, or, respectively, C2 computed scores for the reasons of hiding the truth, in general, or of any level. The moral reasoning stage of the “closest” answer of this moral value only tended to correlate negatively with preference, and the relative preference for the C5 egocentric reasons of hiding the truth of level 2. It correlated negatively also with the preference (as a tendency), and the relative preference (statistically significant) for the C5 mixed reasons of hiding the truth (in which the altruistic

reasons of hiding the truth are in competition with the egocentric ones), as well as positively (statistically significant) with the relative preference for the C5 altruistic reasons of hiding the truth. For C2, it did not correlate with C2 computed scores for the reasons of hiding the truth, in general, or of any level. The mean moral reasoning stage of the “close” answers of this moral value also did not correlate with C5, or C2 computed scores for the reasons of hiding the truth, in general, or of any level. Based on these results, it seems that the level of moral reasoning for this moral value is the least related to the assessed reasons of hiding the truth. Its level of moral reasoning was positively linked with the relative preference for the C5 mixed and altruistic reasons of hiding the truth, but only in the case in which it was assessed based on the “closest” answer.

Considering the results presented above, it is notable that, in comparison with the level of moral reasoning of all the other investigated moral values, the one of the moral value of “truth telling” (the single moral value assessed with SRM-SFO directly related to hiding the truth) was the only one that had a positive relationship with the absolute preference for the altruistic reasons of hiding the truth, particularly for those of level 4, marking its stronger relationship with this kind of reasons of hiding the truth.

Relationship of the scores for the avoidance, and, respectively, approach reasons of hiding the truth computed for C5 (willingness to hide the truth) with the general and item scores of SRM-SFO that indicate moral reasoning maturity and moral value evaluation

The preference for the C5 avoidance reasons of hiding the truth did not correlate with any of the global scores computed for SRM-SFO. It only tended to correlate positively with the preference for the moral reasoning of stage 2 of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO, which is a result in opposition with the correspondent one from Faiciuc (2020). The relative preference for this kind of reasons for hiding the truth tended to correlate positively (as expected) with the SRMS score (but only marginally statistically significant) and, as a weak tendency, with the mean of the stage of “closest” answers at each item of SRMS-SFO, and with the mean of the stage of all “close” answers of SRMS-SFO. These tendencies are in agreement with the positive correlation presented in Faiciuc (2020) between the relative preference for the C5 avoidance reasons of hiding the truth and the index of moral competence of MCT. It also correlated, as expected, negatively (statistically significantly) with the preference for the moral reasoning of stage 1 of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO, and tended to correlate positively with the percentage of stage 3 and 4 of the “closest”, and of the “close” answers at SRM-SFO. In Faiciuc (2020), the relative preference for the C5 reasons of hiding the truth correlated negatively statistically significantly not with the preference for the moral reasoning of stage 1, but with the preference for the moral reasoning of

stage 2, as assessed with MCT, and also correlated positively statistically significantly with the preference for the highest stage (the sixth one) of moral reasoning assessed with MCT (a result in agreement with the tendency toward a positive correlation between relative preference for the C5 reasons of hiding the truth and the percentage of stage 3 and 4 of the “closest”, and of the “close” answers at SRM-SFO).

The preference for the C5 avoidance reasons of hiding the truth correlated negatively with the SRMS score of the item 7 (“**saving the life of a stranger, without losing his or her own life**”, statistically significantly), and with item 8 (“**not taking things that belong to other people**”, as a tendency), whereas the relative preference for the C5 avoidance reasons of hiding the truth tended to correlate positively with the SRMS score of item 8 (“**not taking things that belong to other people**”), and also with the SRMS score of item 9 (“**obeying the law**”), and correlated positively (statistically significantly) with the SRMS score of item 5 (“**children helping their parents**”).

A similar pattern of results was obtained for the link between the preference for the C5 avoidance reasons of hiding the truth and the moral reasoning stage of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO. The preference for the C5 avoidance reasons of hiding the truth correlated negatively (statistically significantly) also with the moral reasoning stage of the “closest” answer for the item 7 (“**saving the life of a stranger (without losing his or her own life)**”), and item 8 (“**not taking things that belong to other people**”), and, supplementary, with the moral reasoning stage of the “closest” answer for the item 2 (“**keeping promises, if you can, to a person you hardly know**”), and 3 (“**parents keeping promises, if they can, to their children**”). The relative preference for the C5 avoidance reasons of hiding the truth correlated positively (statistically significantly), too, with the moral reasoning stage of the “closest” answer for the item 5 (“**children helping their parents**”), and of item 9 (“**obeying the law**”).

Finally, in the case of the mean moral reasoning stage of the “close” answers at SRM-SFO, the preference for the C5 avoidance reasons of hiding the truth only tended to correlate negatively with the mean moral reasoning stage of the “close” answers at item 2 (“**keeping promises, if you can, to a person you hardly know**”). The relative preference for the C5 avoidance reasons of hiding the truth, instead, correlated positively statistically significantly again with the level of moral reasoning of item 5 (“**children helping their parents**”), expressed this time with the mean moral reasoning stage of the “close” answers to it, and also with the mean moral reasoning stage of the “close” answers for item 8 (“**not taking things that belong to other people**”).

So, the preference for the C5 avoidance reasons of hiding the truth was linked negatively with the level of moral reasoning for the items 7, 8, and 2, whereas the relative preference for the C5 avoidance reasons of hiding the truth was linked positively mainly with the level of moral reasoning for the item 5.

The preference for the C5 approach reasons of hiding the truth correlated negatively statistically significantly with the SRMS score for SRM-SFO, with the mean of SRMS score for each item of SRMS-SFO, with the mean of the mean stage of “close” answers at each item of SRMS-SFO, and with the mean of the mean stage of “closest” answers at each item of SRMS-SFO. In the same time, the relative preference for the C5 approach reasons of hiding the truth only tended to correlate negatively with the SRMS score for SRM-SFO, with the mean of the stage of “closest” answers at each item of SRMS-SFO, and with the mean of the stage of all “close” answers of SRMS-SFO. These tendencies obtained for the relative preference for the C5 approach reasons of hiding the truth results are in agreement with the negative correlation obtained in Faiciuc (2020) between the relative preference for the C5 approach reasons of hiding the truth and the index of moral competence of MCT.

The preference for the C5 approach reasons of hiding the truth correlated negatively statistically significantly with the preference for the stage 4 of the moral reasoning of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO, as well as with the percentage of stage 3 and 4 of the “closest”, and, as a tendency, with the preference for the stage 4 of the “close” answers at SRM-SFO. It correlated also positively statistically significantly with the preference for the stage 2 of the moral reasoning of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO. In Faiciuc (2020), the preference for the C5 approach reasons of hiding the truth correlated positively statistically significantly with the preference for the stage 1, and 4 of the moral reasoning, measured with MCT, a result in disagreement with the one obtained in the present study. The relative preference for the C5 approach reasons of hiding the truth correlated, instead, positively statistically significantly with the preference for the stage 1 of the moral reasoning of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO, and tended to correlate negatively with the percentage of stage 3 and 4 of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO, and, respectively, of the “close” answers at SRM-SFO. These results are only in partial agreement with the correspondent ones presented in Faiciuc (2020), because, in that study, the relative preference for the C5 approach reasons of hiding the truth correlated positively with the relative preference for the stage 2, not 1, of the moral reasoning assessed with MCT, and negatively statistically significantly with the preference for the stage 6, the highest one, of the moral reasoning measured with MCT.

Taking into consideration the detailed analysis for each item of SRM-SFO, the preference for the C5 approach reasons of hiding the truth correlated negatively statistically significantly with the SRMS score of item 2 (**“keeping promises, if you can, to a person you hardly know”**), 3 (**“parents keeping promises, if they can, to their children”**), 7 (**“saving the life of a stranger, without losing his or her own life”**), and 8 (**“not taking things that belong to other people”**), and tended to correlate negatively with the SRMS score of item 1 (**“keeping promises, if one can, to friends”**), and 9 (**“obeying the law”**). The relative preference for the

C5 approach reasons of hiding the truth correlated negatively with the SRMS score of item 5 (“**children helping their parents**”, statistically significantly), of item 8 (“**not taking things that belong to other people**”, as a tendency), and item 9 (“**obeying the law**”, as a tendency). The preference for the C5 approach reasons of hiding the truth correlated also negatively statistically significantly with the moral reasoning stage of the “closest” answer for the item 2 (“**keeping promises, if you can, to a person you hardly know**”), 3 (“**parents keeping promises, if they can, to their children**”), 7 (“**saving the life of a stranger, without losing his or her own life**”), and 8 (“**not taking things that belong to other people**”). The relative preference for the C5 approach reasons of hiding the truth correlated negatively statistically significantly only with the moral reasoning stage of the “closest” answer for the item 5 (“**children helping their parents**”), and 9 (“**obeying the law**”). In the case of the mean moral reasoning stage of the “close” answers at SRM-SFO, the preference for the C5 avoidance reasons of hiding the truth correlated negatively statistically significantly with the mean moral reasoning stage of the “close” answers at item 1 (“**keeping promises, if one can, to friends**”), and 9 (“**obeying the law**”), and tended to correlate negatively with this SRM-SFO score of item 2 (“**keeping promises, if you can, to a person you hardly know**”), and 5 (“**children helping their parents**”). The relative preference for the C5 avoidance reasons of hiding the truth correlated negatively statistically significantly, instead, with the mean moral reasoning stage of the “close” answers of item 5 (“**children helping their parents**”), and also with the mean moral reasoning stage of the “close” answers of item 8 (“**not taking things that belong to other people**”). The results of the detailed analysis for the link between the level of moral reasoning of each item of SRM-SFO and the preference or relative preference for the C5 approach reasons of hiding the truth are partially similar to the ones presented above regarding the link between the level of moral reasoning of each item of SRM-SFO and the preference or relative preference for the C5 avoidance reasons of hiding the truth (the results are almost the same for the items 2, 7, and 8 of SRM-SFO). The main difference between them is the positive correlation of the level of moral reasoning of the item 5 (“**children helping their parents**”) of SRM-SFO with the relative preference for the C5 avoidance reasons of hiding the truth, whereas the level of moral reasoning of the item 5 (“**children helping their parents**”) of SRM-SFO had a negative correlation with the relative preference for the C5 approach reasons of hiding the truth. Their similar part is similar also to the obtained correlations between the general score of C5 and the scores for the moral reasoning level for each item of SRM-SFO.

The preference for the avoidance reasons of hiding the truth did not correlate with the MVE scores for any of the moral values investigated with SRM-SFO. Only the preference for the approach reasons of hiding the truth tended to correlate positively with the MVE score for item 10 (“**judges sending people who break the law to jail**”). The relative preference for the avoidance reasons of hiding the

truth, instead, correlated positively statistically significantly with the MVE score for item 7 (“**saving the life of a stranger, without losing his or her own life**”), and tended to correlate positively with MVE for item 3 (“**parents keeping promises, if they can, to their children**”), for item 5 (“**children helping their parents**”), and for item 6 (“**saving the life of a friend, without losing his or her own life**”). The relative preference for the approach reasons of hiding the truth had the reversed pattern of correlations with the MVE scores of SRM-SFO, i.e., with the MVE scores of the same SRM-SFO items, but as tendencies for negative correlations. So, the link of the approach and, respectively, avoidance reasons of hiding the truth with the particular evaluation of the moral values investigated with SRM-SFO is a very weak one, as the only significant association was the positive link between the relative preference for the avoidance reasons of hiding the truth and the importance attributed to the moral value of “**saving the life of a stranger, without losing his or her own life**”.

Relationship of the scores for C5 items with the general scores of SRM-SFO that indicate the moral reasoning maturity and moral value evaluation

In comparison with the results obtained in Faiciuc (2020), and Faiciuc (2016a) regarding the relationship of the scores for the C5 items with the moral competence index of MCT, when only a C5 item (item 12) had a score that correlated statistically significantly positively with the moral competence index, in the current study, many more C5 items had scores that correlated statistically significantly with the global scores of SRM-SFO assessing the level of moral reasoning. Among them was also the above-mentioned item 12 (hiding the truth to avoid the suffering of a close person that would be affected by knowing the truth, part of the scale for reasons of hiding the truth of level 4), which correlated also positively statistically significantly with the SRMS score, and tended to correlate positively with the mean stage of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO. So, this is the C5 item that had the most stable link with the level of moral thinking.

The score for the C5 *item 4*, which, in Faiciuc (2020), and Faiciuc (2016a), correlated statistically significantly positively with the preference for the stage 1 of MCT, in the current study, correlated statistically significantly positively with the preference for the stage 2 of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO (i.e., with the preference for an immature level of moral reasoning, too), and negatively with the preference for the stage 4 of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO. The score for the C5 *item 8*, which, in Faiciuc (2020), and Faiciuc (2016a), correlated statistically significantly positively with the preference for the stage 1 of MCT, in the current study, correlated statistically significantly positively with the preference for the stage 2 of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO, and negatively with the preference for the stage 4 of the “closest” and “close” answers at SRM-SFO, but also tended to

correlate positively with the preference for the stage 1, and stage 3 of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO. A similar pattern of results was obtained in the case of the score for the *C5 item 14*, which, in Faiciuc (2020), and Faiciuc (2016a), correlated statistically significantly positively with the preference for the stage 1 of MCT, but, in the current study, correlated statistically significantly positively with the preference for the stage 2 of the “closest”, and “close” answers at SRM-SFO, with the preference for the stage 3 of the “close” answers at SRM-SFO, and negatively with the preference for the stage 4 of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO. Likewise, the score for the *C5 item 17*, which, in Faiciuc (2020), and Faiciuc (2016a), correlated positively with the preference for the stage 1 of MCT (statistically significantly), with the preference for the stage 2 of MCT (statistically significantly in the study from 2020, and as a tendency in the study from 2016), with the preference for the stage 3 of MCT (statistically significantly in the study from 2016, and as a tendency in the study from 2020), and with the preference for the stage 4 of MCT (statistically significantly), in the current study, correlated statistically significantly positively with the preference for the stage 2 of the “closest”, and “close” answers at SRM-SFO, and negatively with the preference for the stage 4 of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO. The score for the *C5 item 18*, which, in Faiciuc (2020), and Faiciuc (2016a), correlated statistically significantly positively with the preference for the stage 1 of MCT, in the current study, correlated statistically significantly positively with the preference for the stage 3 of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO, and negatively with the preference for the stage 4 of the “closest”, and “close” answers at SRM-SFO. The score for the *C5 item 19*, instead, which, in Faiciuc (2020), and Faiciuc (2016a), correlated statistically significantly positively with the preference for the stage 1 of MCT, in the current study, correlated statistically significantly positively also with the preference for the stage 1 of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO, and negatively with the preference for the stage 4 of the “closest”, and “close” answers at SRM-SFO. It tended also to correlate positively with the preference for the stage 2 of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO, and negatively with the preference for the stage 3 of the “close” answers at SRM-SFO. The case for the *C5 item 30* was similar to the one for the *C5 item 19*, as, in Faiciuc (2020), and Faiciuc (2016a), its score correlated statistically significantly positively with the preference for the stage 1 of MCT, and, in the current study, it correlated statistically significantly positively, too, with the preference for the stage 1 of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO, and negatively with the preference for the stage 4 of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO. It tended also to correlate positively with the preference for the stage 2 of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO.

The score for the *C5 item 9*, which, in Faiciuc (2020), and Faiciuc (2016a) correlated statistically significantly positively with the preference for the stage 2 of MCT, in the current study, correlated also statistically significantly positively with the preference for the stage 2 of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO, and with the preference for the stage 3 of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO, and negatively with

the preference for the stage 4 of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO (it only tended to correlate negatively with the preference for the stage 4 of the “close” answers at SRM-SFO). The score for the C5 *item 13*, which, in Faiciuc (2020), correlated statistically significantly negatively with the preference for the stage 2 of MCT (in the study from 2016 only tended to have a negative correlation with the preference for the stage 2 of MCT), in the current study, only tended to correlate negatively with the preference for the stage 2 of the “closest”, and “close” answers at SRM-SFO, and positively with the preference for the stage 4 of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO. The score for the C5 *item 31*, which, in Faiciuc (2016a), correlated statistically significantly positively (unexpectedly) with the preference for the stage 2 of MCT (in the study from 2020 only tended to have a positive correlation with the preference for the stage 2 of MCT), in the current study, only tended to correlate positively with the preference for the stage 2 of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO, and correlated statistically significantly negatively with the preference for the stage 4 of the “closest” answers at SRM-SFO (it only tended to correlate negatively with the preference for the stage 4 of the “close” answers at SRM-SFO).

The scores for the C5 *item 24*, and C5 *item 28*, which in Faiciuc (2020), and Faiciuc (2016a) correlated statistically significantly positively with the preference for the stage 1 of MCT, in the current study did not have any relationship with the preference for the stages of moral reasoning assessed with SRM-SFO. Likewise, the score for the C5 *item 16*, which, in Faiciuc (2020) correlated statistically significantly positively with the preference for the stage 4 of MCT, in the current study, did not have any relationship with the preference for the stages of moral reasoning assessed with SRM-SFO.

So, the most stable results regarding the relationship of the scores for the C5 items with the preference for the stages of moral reasoning were the one regarding the items **19** (*I gave in / would give in to the temptation to hide the truth, thinking that it would not be such a heavy burden on my conscience.*), **30** (*I decided / would decide to hide the truth, thinking that telling the truth is something that has little value in the society in which I live, being little respected*), and **9** (*I decided / would decide to hide the truth when the person or people I hid / would hide it from also hid something from me*), and, to a lesser extent, **13** (*I preferred / would prefer to hide the truth in order to avoid causing suffering to a stranger who would have been / would be affected by finding out the truth*), and **31** (*I decided / would decide to hide the truth, thinking that, for the good of society, it is something more important than telling the truth, other values taking precedence*).

FINAL CONCLUSIONS

The relationship of the reasons of hiding the truth with the level of moral reasoning has been investigated in the current study and in the two previous cited ones using a triangulation strategy in order to see which results remain stable when

changing the instruments that were used for its investigation, and as a mean to compensate for the small volume of the available samples. There was a partial overlap of the results obtained in the three considered studies. The most stable result was the expected positive relationship of the level of moral reasoning or moral competence with the absolute or relative preference for the altruistic reasons of level 4, which represent altruistic reasons of hiding the truth linked with a kind of morality placed at a social micro level. A stable result was also the expected negative relationship of the preference or relative preference for egocentric reasons of hiding the truth with the level of moral reasoning. The results from the current study in which a negative relationship was found between the general willingness to hide the truth and the level of moral reasoning, as well as a negative relationship of the tendency to consider hiding the truth as justified with the importance attributed in general to moral values, investigated with SRM-SFO, are in agreement with some of the studies cited in the introductory part, which present data supporting a positive relationship between the honest behavior and the level of moral reasoning (or, correlatively, a negative relationship of cheating, lying, antisocial or delinquent behavior with the level of moral reasoning) as assessed with various instruments based on the Kohlbergian theory.

The present study also brings new data regarding the particular relationship of the level of moral reasoning for the moral value of truth telling and the self-reported evaluation of this moral value with the willingness to hide the truth in various situations (assessed with the self-reported behavioral and attitudinal measure of C5), or, respectively, with the tendency to consider hiding the truth as justified in those situations (assessed with the self-reported attitudinal measure of C2). This relationship was compared with the correspondent relationships in the cases of the other values that were investigated with SRM-SFO. The most notable difference was the positive relationship of the level of reasoning for truth telling with the absolute preference for the C5 altruistic reasons of hiding the truth, particularly of level 4. In the same time, the willingness to hide the truth in various situations, or, respectively, the tendency to consider hiding the truth as justified in those situations had also significant associations, generally in the expected directions, with the level of moral reasoning for most of the other moral values that were investigated with SRM-SFO, and with the self-reported importance attributed to them, sometimes even stronger than the ones obtained in the case of the moral value of truth telling. These data are in agreement with the data obtained in the current study that suggest a negative link of the general level of moral reasoning as measured with some of the SRM-SFO scores, no matter the domain, with the self-reported willingness to hide the truth, and a negative link of the moral value evaluation in general with the tendency to consider hiding the truth as justified. They indicate that the self-reported position regarding hiding/telling the truth might be connected with the general level of moral reasoning of a person and with the way she/he evaluates different moral values. In the same time, the obtained data

also suggest, in agreement with the opinion and its supporting data cited in the introductory part, that the relationship of cheating behavior that involves also lying with the moral reasoning level may be conditioned by particular contexts, that the link between the self-reported position regarding hiding the truth and the level of moral reasoning depends on the respondent's preferred reasons to hide the truth, on the moral domain in which her/his moral reasoning is assessed, and on the way her/his position regarding hiding the truth, and her/his level of moral reasoning are evaluated.

The above-mentioned results offer also useful information regarding the convergent validity of the four instruments that were used in the series of the three studies, i.e., the current one, the one presented in Faiciuc (2016a), and the one presented in Faiciuc (2020). They support the most the convergent validity of the SRM-SFO and C5 measures.

In the interpretation of the obtained data, the limits of the current research should be taken into consideration, among which are the relatively small number of participants, the insufficient data regarding the psychometric qualities of the used instruments, the fact they are self-reported measurements, the low internal consistencies of some of their scales, the homogenous samples, composed of students at fine arts, mostly females. Further studies are needed to overcome these limits and to find out which of the results from the current exploratory study are replicable. Such studies should extend the research by using larger and more heterogeneous samples, new instruments, and more sophisticated methods for data analyses.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Aleixo, P. A., & Norris, C. E. (2000). Personality and moral reasoning in young offenders. *Personality and individual differences*, 28(3), 609–623.
- Ashkar, P. J., & Kenny, D. T. (2007). Moral reasoning of adolescent male offenders: Comparison of sexual and nonsexual offenders. *Criminal Justice and Behavior*, 34(1), 108–118.
- Barriga, A. Q., Morrison, E. M., Liau, A. K., & Gibbs, J. C. (2001). Moral cognition: Explaining the gender difference in antisocial behavior. *Merrill-Palmer Quarterly* (1982–), 532–562.
- Basinger, K. S., Brugman, D., & Gibbs, J. C. (2007). *Social Reflection Questionnaire – SFO*. Unpublished material, Urbana University, OH, USA, and the University of Utrecht, the Netherlands. Retrieved in 2.03. 2010 at https://www.academia.edu/3757930/Sociomoral_Reflection_Measure_Short_Form_Objective
- Bear, G. G., & Richards, H. C. (1981). Moral reasoning and conduct problems in the classroom. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 73(5), 664–670.
- Beerthuisen, M. G., & Brugman, D. (2013). Moral value evaluation: A neglected motivational concept in externalizing behaviour research. In K. Heinrichs, F. Oser, & T. Lovat (Eds.), *Handbook of moral motivation: What makes people act morally right?* (pp. 365–384). Rotterdam: Sense Publishers.
- Beerthuisen, M. G., & Brugman, D. (2016). The relationship of moral value evaluation with externalizing behaviour across value areas in adolescents. *European Journal of Developmental Psychology*, 13(1), 84–98.

- Beerthuizen, M. G., Brugman, D., & Basinger, K. S. (2013). Oppositional defiance, moral reasoning and moral value evaluation as predictors of self-reported juvenile delinquency. *Journal of Moral Education*, 42(4), 460–474.
- Beerthuizen, M. G. C. J. (2012). *The impact of morality on externalizing behavior; values, reasoning, cognitive distortions and identity*. Utrecht, The Netherlands: Drukkerij Zuidam & Uithof.
- Boessenkool, C. (2023). *Assessing moral judgment maturity using the Defining Issues Test (DIT-2) and the Sociomoral Reflection Measure-Short Form Objective (SRM-SFO)* (Master's thesis). Accessed in 10.06.2024 at <https://studenttheses.uu.nl/handle/20.500.12932/43435>
- Bruggeman, E. L., & Hart, K. J. (1996). Cheating, lying, and moral reasoning by religious and secular high school students. *The Journal of Educational Research*, 89(6), 340–344.
- Brugman, D., & Aleva, A. E. (2004). Developmental delay or regression in moral reasoning by juvenile delinquents?. *Journal of Moral Education*, 33(3), 321–338.
- Brugman, D., Basinger, K. S., & Gibbs, J. C. (2007). *Measuring adolescents' moral judgment: An evaluation of the sociomoral reflection measure–Short Form Objective (SRM-SFO)*. Unpublished manuscript, University of Utrecht & Urbana University. Accessed in 10.05.2020 at https://www.academia.edu/4594794/Measuring_Adolescents_Moral_Judgment_An_Evaluation_of_the_Sociomoral_Reflection_Measure_-_Short_Form_Objective_SRM-SFO
- Cabin, R. J., & Mitchell, R. J. (2000). To Bonferroni or not to Bonferroni: when and how are the questions. *Bulletin of the ecological society of America*, 81(3), 246–248.
- Campagna, A. F., & Harter, S. (1975). Moral judgment in sociopathic and normal children. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 31(2), 199–205.
- Chung, J. O., & Hsu, S. H. (2017). The effect of cognitive moral development on honesty in managerial reporting. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 145, 563–575.
- Faiciuc, L.-E. (2015). Moral Competence and Socio-Moral Reflection. *Anuarul Institutului de Istorie „George Barițiu” din Cluj-Napoca, Series Humanistica* (“*The Annual Review (Yearbook) of the «George Barițiu» History Institute in Cluj-Napoca, Series Humanistica*”), vol. XIII, 73–89. http://www.humanistica.ro/anuare/2015/Continut/Faiciuc%20Humanistica_2015.pdf
- Faiciuc, L.-E. (2016a). Competența morală și motivațiile comportamentului de a ascunde adevărul. [Moral Competence and the Reasons of the Behavior of hiding the truth]. *Anuarul Institutului de Istorie „George Barițiu” din Cluj-Napoca, Series Humanistica*, XIV, 73–89.
- Faiciuc, L.-E. (2016b). Evaluarea judecății morale din perspectiva condițiilor în care o acțiune imorală este considerată justificată [The evaluation of moral judgment from the perspective of the conditions in which an immoral action is considered justified]. *Studii și cercetări din domeniul științelor socio-umane*, 29, 162–176
- Faiciuc, L.-E. (2020). Reasons for hiding the truth and their relationship with moral competence and emotion regulation. *Anuarul Institutului de Istorie „George Barițiu” din Cluj-Napoca, Series Humanistica* (“*The Annual Review (Yearbook) of the «George Barițiu» History Institute in Cluj-Napoca, Series Humanistica*”), vol. XVIII, 69–160. http://www.humanistica.ro/anuare/2020/Continut/07-HUMANISTICA_2020%20-%20Faiciuc.pdf
- Faiciuc, L.-E. (2021). Emotion regulation goals and their relationship with moral competence, moral orientation, and the type of motivation for hiding the truth. *Anuarul Institutului de Istorie „George Barițiu” din Cluj-Napoca, Series Humanistica* (“*The Annual Review (Yearbook) of the «George Barițiu» History Institute in Cluj-Napoca, Series Humanistica*”), vol. XIX, 19–128. http://www.humanistica.ro/anuare/2021/Continut/05-HUMANISTICA_2021.pdf
- Gardiner, S. (2019). *An empirical investigation of Barriga's mediational model of moral cognition and antisocial behaviour: Moral reasoning recognition versus response generation assessments in models for general delinquency and sexually coercive behaviours*. Master Thesis, University of Windsor. Electronic Theses and Dissertations. 7808. <https://scholar.uwindsor.ca/etd/7808>
- Gibbs, J. C. (1979). Kohlberg's moral stage theory: A Piagetian revision. *Human Development*, 22, 89–112.

- Gibbs, J. C. (2003). Equipping youth with mature moral judgment. *Reclaiming children and youth*, 12(3), 148–153.
- Gibbs, J. C., Basinger, K. S., & Fuller, D. (1992). *Moral maturity: Measuring the development of sociomoral reflection*. Hillsdale, NJ: Erlbaum.
- Gregg, V., Gibbs, J. C., & Basinger, K. S. (1994). Patterns of developmental delay in moral judgment by male and female delinquents. *Merrill-Palmer Quarterly*, 40(4), 538–553.
- Halevy, R., Shalvi, S., & Verschuere, B. (2014). Being honest about dishonesty: Correlating self-reports and actual lying. *Human Communication Research*, 40(1), 54–72.
- Heyns, P. M., van Niekerk, H. G., & Le Roux, J. A. (1981). Moral judgment and behavioral dimensions of juvenile delinquency. *International Journal for the Advancement of Counselling*, 4, 139–151.
- Jurkovic, G. J. (1980). The juvenile delinquent as a moral philosopher: A structural-developmental perspective. *Psychological Bulletin*, 88(3), 709–727.
- Kupfersmid, J. H., & Wonderly, D. M. (1980). Moral maturity and behavior: Failure to find a link. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 9(3), 249–261.
- Langdon, P. E., Murphy, G. H., Clare, I. C. H., & Palmer, E. J. (2010). The psychometric properties of the Socio-Moral Reflection Measure-Short Form and the Moral Theme Inventory for men with and without intellectual disabilities. *Research in Developmental Disabilities*, 31, 1204–1215.
- Langdon, P. E., Murphy, G. H., Clare, I. C. H., Steverson, T., & Palmer, E. J. (2011). Relationships among moral reasoning, empathy, and distorted cognitions in men with intellectual disabilities and a history of criminal offending. *American Journal on Intellectual and Developmental Disabilities*, 116, 438–456.
- Lardén, M., Melin, L., Holst, U., & Långström, N. (2006). Moral judgement, cognitive distortions and empathy in incarcerated delinquent and community control adolescents. *Psychology, Crime & Law*, 12(5), 453–462.
- Leming, J. S. (1978). Cheating behavior, situational influence, and moral development. *The Journal of Educational Research*, 71(4), 214–217.
- Lind, G. (1978). Wie misst man moralisches Urteil? Probleme und alternative Möglichkeiten der Messung eines komplexen Konstrukts [How Does One Measure Moral Judgment? Problems and Alternative Possibilities of Measuring a Complex Construct]. In G. Portele (Ed.), *Sozialisation und moral [Socialization and morality]* (pp. 171–201). Weinheim, Germany: Beltz.
- Lind, G. (1985). The theory of moral cognitive development. A socio-psychological assessment. In G. Lind, H. A. Hartmann, & R. H. Wakenhut (Eds.), *Moral development and the social environment* (pp. 21–53). Chicago: Precedent Publishing.
- Littler, K. (2015). *Cognitive and affective processes associated with moral reasoning, and their relationship with behaviour in typical development*. PhD Thesis, University of Exeter (United Kingdom). Accessed in 10.02.2023 at <https://ore.exeter.ac.uk/repository/bitstream/handle/10871/18168/LittlerK.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>
- Makowski, D., Pham, T., Lau, Z., Dayton, L. W. Y., Raine, A., & Chen, S. (2020, March 10). *The Structure of Deception: Validation of the Lying Profile Questionnaire*. Retrieved in 2.02.2024 from <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/t7s32>
- Malinowski, C. I., & Smith, C. P. (1985). Moral reasoning and moral conduct: An investigation prompted by Kohlberg's theory. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 49(4), 1016–1027.
- Matsueda, R. L. (1989). The dynamics of moral beliefs and minor deviance. *Social Forces*, 68(2), 428–457.

- McColgan, E. B., Rest, J. R., & Pruitt, D. B. (1983). Moral judgment and antisocial behavior in early adolescence. *Journal of applied developmental psychology, 4*(2), 189–199.
- McDermott, E., & Langdon, P. E. (2016). The moral reasoning abilities of men and women with intellectual disabilities who have a history of criminal offending behaviour. *Legal and Criminological Psychology, 21*(1), 25–40.
- Nelson, J. R., Smith, D. J., & Dodd, J. (1990). The moral reasoning of juvenile delinquents: A meta-analysis. *Journal of abnormal child psychology, 18*, 231–239.
- O'Kane, A., Fawcett, D., & Blackburn, R. (1996). Psychopathy and moral reasoning: Comparison of two classifications. *Personality and Individual Differences, 20*(4), 505–514.
- Oosterlaken, A. (2013). *Bridging the gap between moral judgment and antisocial behavior?* Master thesis, Utrecht University. Accessed in 23.05.2023 at <https://studenttheses.uu.nl/bitstream/handle/20.500.12932/12399/Oosterlaken%203414221.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>
- Palmer, E. J. (2003). An overview of the relationship between moral reasoning and offending. *Australian Psychologist, 38*(3), 165–174.
- Palmer, E. J., & Hollin, C. R. (1998). A comparison of patterns of moral development in young offenders and non-offenders. *Legal and Criminological Psychology, 3*(2), 225–235.
- Petronio, R. J. (1980). The moral maturity of repeater delinquents. *Youth and Society, 12*, 51–59
- Ponemon, L. A. (1992). Auditor underreporting of time and moral reasoning: An experimental lab study. *Contemporary Accounting Research, 9*(1), 171–189.
- Raaijmakers, Q., Engels, R., & Van Hoof, A. (2005). Delinquency and moral reasoning in adolescence and young adulthood. *International Journal of Behavioral Development, 29*(3), 247–258.
- Renwick, S., & Emler, N. (1984). Moral reasoning and delinquent behaviour among students. *British Journal of Social Psychology, 23*(3), 281–283.
- Santrock, J. W. (1975). Moral structure: The interrelations of moral behavior, moral judgment, and moral affect. *The Journal of Genetic Psychology, 127*(2), 201–213.
- Shields, D. L., Funk, C. D., & Bredemeier, B. L. (2018). Relationships among moral and contesting variables and prosocial and antisocial behavior in sport. *Journal of Moral Education, 47*(1), 17–33.
- Smetana, J. (1990). Morality and conduct disorders. In M. Lewis & S. M. Miller (Eds.), *Handbook of developmental psychopathology* (pp. 157–179). New York, NY: Plenum.
- Stams, G. J., Brugman, D., Deković, M., Van Rosmalen, L., Van Der Laan, P., & Gibbs, J. C. (2006). The moral judgment of juvenile delinquents: A meta-analysis. *Journal of abnormal child psychology, 34*, 692–708.
- Stevenson, S. F., Hall, G., & Innes, J. M. (2004). Rationalizing criminal behaviour: The influence of criminal sentiments on sociomoral development in violent offenders and nonoffenders. *International Journal of Offender Therapy and Comparative Criminology, 48*(2), 161–174.
- Streiner, D. L. (2015). Best (but oft-forgotten) practices: the multiple problems of multiplicity—whether and how to correct for many statistical tests. *The American journal of clinical nutrition, 102*(4), 721–728.
- Tarry, H., & Emler, N. (2007). Attitudes, values and moral reasoning as predictors of delinquency. *British Journal of Developmental Psychology, 25*(2), 169–183.
- Wright, J. D. (2015). *An examination of the effects of moral maturity, propensity for moral disengagement, entitlement perceptions and anomia on fraud behavior* (Doctoral dissertation, The Chicago School of Professional Psychology. Accessed in 23.06.2023 at https://www.academia.edu/23740823/An_Examination_of_the_Effects_of_Moral_Maturity_Propensity_for_Moral_Disengagement_Entitlement_Perceptions_and_Anomia_on_Fraud_Behavior

APPENDIX 1

C5 Questionnaire – English version

QUESTIONNAIRE FOR THE MOTIVATION ASSESSMENT IN A DILEMMATIC SITUATION – EXPERIMENTAL VERSION

The items of the questionnaire from below aim to study how a person motivates a certain behavior in a dilemma situation or an impasse: whether or not to hide the truth, in circumstances that may or may not support one or the other of the alternatives.

Please answer these items based on your recent experience and on how you personally think about each of the considered circumstances, specifying the extent to which the statements made are valid or appropriate in your case. To do this, next to the number corresponding to each item in the table from the answer sheet, you will need to mark with an X the box corresponding to the answer you have chosen from the indicated options.

The results are useful for an empirical research. Therefore, you are asked to try to be as accurate as possible in completing the answers, so that the results of the research are undistorted.

We assure the confidentiality of your answers. Thank you!

1. I gave in / would give in to the temptation to hide the truth in order to avoid personal physical suffering or material loss.
2. I have accepted / would agree to hide the truth when I have been asked / would be asked to do so by a person who has authority over me in some way.
3. I decided / would decide to hide the truth, too, when I found out / would find out that people with authority close to me or respected in society have done so in the past.
4. I gave in / would give in to the temptation to hide the truth in order to gain something material in exchange for silence.
5. I gave in / would give in to the temptation to hide the truth if I knew that the danger of me suffering an important negative consequence for myself because of doing that was small.
6. I gave in / would give in to the temptation to hide an uncomfortable truth when I had / would have the certainty that the hidden truth will remain hidden forever.
7. I preferred / would prefer to hide an uncomfortable truth when there was / would be missing an express request for me to say it, because it was / is not suspected by others.
8. I decided / would decide that I could hide the truth when I found out / would find out that other colleagues or friends of mine did / do the same.
9. I decided / would decide to hide the truth when the person or people I hid / would hide it from also hid something from me.
10. I preferred / would prefer to hide the truth in order to keep my relationship with a person I care about, who is important to me.
11. I decided / would decide to hide the truth in order to spare the feelings of a stranger to me.
12. I preferred / would prefer to hide the truth in order to avoid causing suffering to a close person who would have been / would be affected by finding out the truth.

13. I preferred / would prefer to hide the truth in order to avoid causing suffering to a stranger who would have been / would be affected by finding out the truth.

14. I preferred / would prefer to hide the truth in order to bring an advantage through my silence to a close person who needed / would need this advantage.

15. I preferred / would prefer to hide the truth in order to bring an advantage through my silence to a stranger who needed / would need this advantage.

16. I preferred / would prefer to hide the truth in order to avoid that a group of close people, or the community to which I belong to suffer some loss.

17. I preferred / would prefer to hide the truth in order to bring an advantage to a close group or to the community to which I belong.

18. I preferred / would prefer to hide the truth if, in the community I am part of, hiding the truth is something common, easily accepted, or tolerated.

19. I gave in / would give in to the temptation to hide the truth, thinking that it would not be such a heavy burden on my conscience.

20. I gave in / would give in to the temptation to hide the truth, thinking that the rebukes of conscience would affect me less than what would have happened / what would happen by confessing it.

21. I gave in / would give in to the temptation to hide the truth because of the shame I would have had / would have if I had said it / I said it.

22. I have decided / would decide to hide the truth out of fear that I will not be understood by those around me if I told it, and that they might ridicule me.

23. I gave in / would give in to the temptation to hide the truth in order to gain, or keep a good reputation or image in the eyes of others.

24. I decided / would decide to hide the truth because the reputation of being an honest person, who tells the truth, is not that important to me.

25. I decided / would decide to hide the truth, thinking that telling the truth is something relative, subjective, which depends on one's perspective on a situation, having no value in itself.

26. I preferred / would prefer to hide the truth in order to respect another principle or human value that I am guided by in my decisions, which was / would be more important, in my opinion.

27. I decided / would decide to hide the truth, thinking that, in this way, I could protect the society in which I live from a danger.

28. I decided / would decide to hide the truth, thinking that, in this way, I could bring a benefit to the society in which I live.

29. I decided / would decide to hide the truth, thinking that my individual decisions are too small and insignificant to be able to influence society in any way.

30. I decided / would decide to hide the truth, thinking that telling the truth is something that has little value in the society in which I live, being little respected.

31. I decided / would decide to hide the truth, thinking that, for the good of society, it is something more important than telling the truth, other values taking precedence.

Answer sheet

	Not at all	To a small extent	To a moderate extent	To a large extent	Entirely
Item 1					

Level 1: Items 4, 5, 19, 24, 25, 29

Level 2: Items 3, 9, 8, 18, 30

Level 3: Items 1, 2, 6, 7, 20, 21, 22, 23

Level 4: Items 10, 12, 14,

Level 5: Items 11, 13, 15, 16, 17, 26, 27, 28, 31

Avoidance cluster of C5: bolded items

Approach cluster of C5: items without bolded words

Altruism cluster of C5: Items 2, 3, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 27, 28

Egocentrism-altruism cluster of C5: Items 1, 5, 6, 7, 10, 20, 21, 22, 23

Egocentrism cluster of C5: Items 4, 8, 9, 17, 18, 19, 24, 25, 26, 29, 30, 31

APPENDIX 2

C2 Questionnaire – English version

QUESTIONNAIRE FOR THE MOTIVATION ASSESSMENT IN A DILEMMATIC SITUATION -EXPERIMENTAL VERSION

The items of the questionnaire from below aim to study how a person motivates a certain behavior in a dilemma situation or an impasse: whether or not to hide the truth, in circumstances that may or may not support one or the other of the alternatives.

Please answer these items based on your recent experience and on how you personally think about each of the considered circumstances, specifying the extent to which the statements made are valid or appropriate in your case. To do this, next to the number corresponding to each item in the table from the answer sheet, you will need to mark with an X the box corresponding to the answer you have chosen from the indicated options.

The results are useful for an empirical research. Therefore, you are asked to try to be as accurate as possible in completing the answers, so that the results of the research are undistorted.

We assure the confidentiality of your answers. Thank you!

1. It is justified to hide the truth in order to avoid punishment or an immediate material disadvantage.
2. It is justified to hide the truth so that the achievement of the personal goals to remain unaffected.
3. It is justified to hide the truth if it is helpful to the achievement of the personal ends.
4. It is justified to hide the truth in order to obtain an advantage or an immediate material gain.
5. It is justified to hide the truth to avoid punishment or a disadvantage that might occur sometime, in the long run.
6. It is justified to hide the truth in order to obtain an advantage or a material gain that might occur sometime, in the long run.
7. It is justified to hide the truth when the possible negative consequences of confessing it will quickly pass or be forgotten.

8. It is justified to hide the truth if it will remain also a secret in the future, because no one else will be able to know it.
9. It is justified to hide the truth when there is no express request to tell it.
10. It is justified to hide the truth when you are asked to do so by a person who has authority over you.
11. It is justified to hide the truth from someone who has lied to you.
12. It is justified to hide the truth when others in your group of acquaintances have the habit of hiding the truth.
13. It is justified to hide the truth when you realize that important people in society or in community have done it.
14. It is justified to hide the truth when you consider that concealing it is without harmful consequences for someone close to you.
15. It is justified to hide the truth when you consider that concealing it is without harmful consequences for someone who is a stranger.
16. It is justified to hide the truth when doing so may help someone close to you.
17. It is justified to hide the truth when doing so can help a stranger.
18. It is justified to hide the truth in order to maintain a relationship with someone.
19. It is justified to hide the truth in order to help the group/collectivity to which you belong.
20. It is justified to hide the truth when, in the community in which you live, the truth is valued quite little.
21. It is justified to hide the truth because truth is relative and subjective, depending on the perspective from which one views a situation.
22. It is justified to hide the truth when the guilty conscience would be easier to bear than what you would feel if you told it.
23. It is justified to hide the truth if the feeling of guilty conscience for your silence was not important.
24. It is justified to hide the truth when your reputation as a honest man, who tells the truth, is of little importance to you.
25. It is justified to hide the truth in order to gain or keep a good reputation or image in the eyes of others.
26. It is justified to hide the truth when doing so can protect society from a danger or help it in some way.
27. It is justified to hide the truth when in the society in which you live, as a whole, telling the truth has little value, being little respected.
28. It is justified to hide the truth when, for you, other human values are more important.
29. It is justified to hide the truth because for the good of society there may be human reasons or values that are more important than telling the truth, and these should prevail.
30. It is justified to hide the truth because an individual decision is too small and insignificant to have any effect on society.
31. There is no justification for hiding the truth in any situation, regardless of the context.

Answer sheet

**Yes, it is in agreement with
what I think**

**No, it is not in agreement with
what I think**

Item 1

- Level 1:** Items 2, 3, 4, 6, 21, 24, 30
Level 2: Items 10, 11, 12, 13, 20, 27
Level 3: Items 1, 5, 7, 8, 9, 25, 22, 23
Level 4: Items 14, 15, 18
Level 5: Items 16, 17, 19, 26, 28, 29

APPENDIX 3

Table 20

Rank Spearman correlations of the scores for C5 items with the global scores of moral reasoning, and moral value evaluation of SRM-SFO

		SRMS	Mean of SRMS of each item of SRMS-SFO	MVE	Mean of the mean stage of "close" answers at each item of SRMS-SFO	Mean of the stage of "closest" answers at each item of SRMS-SFO	Mean of the stage of all "close" answers of SRMS-SFO
C5 item 1	ρ coefficient	-.001	-.117	-.151	-.105	-.119	.221
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.498	.273	.174	.278	.245	.088
	N	34	29	41	34	36	39
C5 item 2	ρ coefficient	-.408**	-.460**	-.127	-.341*	-.363*	-.264
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.008	.006	.215	.024	.015	.052
	N	34	29	41	34	36	39
C5 item 3	ρ coefficient	-.482**	-.463**	-.387**	-.361*	-.486**	-.286*
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.002	.006	.006	.018	.001	.039
	N	34	29	41	34	36	39
C5 item 4	ρ coefficient	-.353*	-.386*	-.256	-.328*	-.389**	-.199
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.020	.019	.053	.029	.010	.113
	N	34	29	41	34	36	39
C5 item 5	ρ coefficient	-.276	-.370*	-.113	-.335*	-.275	-.187
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.057	.024	.240	.026	.053	.128
	N	34	29	41	34	36	39
C5 item 6	ρ coefficient	-.323*	-.412*	.104	-.289*	-.271	-.199
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.031	.013	.259	.049	.055	.112
	N	34	29	41	34	36	39
C5 item 7	ρ coefficient	-.137	-.092	.030	-.036	-.182	-.024
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.220	.317	.427	.420	.144	.443
	N	34	29	41	34	36	39
C5 item 8	ρ coefficient	-.509**	-.484**	-.248	-.175	-.553**	-.011
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.001	.004	.059	.161	.000	.475
	N	34	29	41	34	36	39
C5 item 9	ρ coefficient	-.335*	-.336*	-.154	-.219	-.371*	-.091
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.026	.038	.168	.107	.013	.291
	N	34	29	41	34	36	39
C5 item 10	ρ coefficient	.230	.190	-.340*	.440**	.114	.434**
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.096	.161	.015	.005	.254	.003
	N	34	29	41	34	36	39
C5 item 11	ρ coefficient	.382	.317	.014	.149	.266	.234
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.013	.047	.465	.200	.058	.076
	N	34	29	41	34	36	39
C5 item 12	ρ coefficient	.287	.194	-.056	.160	.231	.167
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.050	.156	.365	.183	.087	.155
	N	34	29	41	34	36	39
C5 item 13	ρ coefficient	.321*	.328*	.077	.029	.230	.108
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.032	.041	.315	.435	.089	.257
	N	34	29	41	34	36	39
C5 item 14	ρ coefficient	-.340*	-.335*	.032	-.197	-.320*	-.117
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.025	.038	.421	.132	.029	.239
	N	34	29	41	34	36	39
C5 item 15	ρ coefficient	-.245	-.221	.171	-.290*	-.224	-.268*
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.081	.124	.142	.048	.095	.049
	N	34	29	41	34	36	39
C5 item 16	ρ coefficient	.016	-.122	.215	-.268	-.013	-.083
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.464	.265	.088	.063	.471	.308
	N	34	29	41	34	36	39
C5 item 17	ρ coefficient	-.328*	-.449**	.075	-.362*	-.356*	-.181
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.029	.007	.321	.018	.017	.135
	N	34	29	41	34	36	39
C5 item 18	ρ coefficient	-.375*	-.338*	-.468**	-.055	-.451**	.013
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.014	.037	.001	.378	.003	.468
	N	34	29	41	34	36	39

		SRMS	Mean of SRMS of each item of SRMS-SFO	MVE	Mean of the mean stage of "close" answers at each item of SRMS-SFO	Mean of the stage of "closest" answers at each item of SRMS-SFO	Mean of the stage of all "close" answers of SRMS-SFO
C5 item 19	ρ coefficient	-.370*	-.428*	-.336*	-.206	-.439**	-.029
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.016	.010	.016	.122	.004	.430
	N	34	29	41	34	36	39
C5 item 20	ρ coefficient	-.003	-.130	-.206	-.044	-.082	.093
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.493	.251	.098	.402	.318	.287
	N	34	29	41	34	36	39
C5 item 21	ρ coefficient	.094	.024	.172	-.305*	.019	-.137
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.298	.451	.141	.039	.456	.203
	N	34	29	41	34	36	39
C5 item 22	ρ coefficient	-.101	-.060	.156	-.211	-.121	-.080
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.286	.378	.166	.116	.240	.315
	N	34	29	41	34	36	39
C5 item 23	ρ coefficient	-.201	-.193	-.078	.033	-.259	.006
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.128	.158	.314	.427	.064	.485
	N	34	29	41	34	36	39
C5 item 24	ρ coefficient	-.003	.011	-.060	-.125	-.003	-.154
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.494	.478	.356	.240	.492	.177
	N	33	29	40	34	35	38
C5 item 25	ρ coefficient	.153	.054	-.057	-.142	.078	-.074
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.197	.392	.361	.215	.327	.329
	N	33	28	41	33	35	38
C5 item 26	ρ coefficient	.129	.239	-.024	.150	.060	.096
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.233	.106	.441	.199	.364	.281
	N	34	29	40	34	36	39
C5 item 27	ρ coefficient	-.195	-.078	.139	-.112	-.165	-.218
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.135	.344	.196	.265	.171	.091
	N	34	29	40	34	35	39
C5 item 28	ρ coefficient	-.121	-.071	.098	-.123	-.073	-.118
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.248	.357	.272	.244	.337	.237
	N	34	29	41	34	36	39
C5 item 29	ρ coefficient	-.350*	-.387*	-.252	-.218	-.380*	-.068
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.021	.019	.056	.108	.011	.341
	N	34	29	41	34	36	39
C5 item 30	ρ coefficient	-.353*	-.428*	-.223	-.141	-.375*	.023
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.020	.010	.080	.213	.012	.445
	N	34	29	41	34	36	39
C5 item 31	ρ coefficient	-.296*	-.265	-.429**	-.283	-.341*	-.055
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.045	.082	.003	.053	.021	.371
	N	34	29	41	34	36	39

* $p < .05$ ** $p < .01$

Table 21

Rank Spearman correlations of the scores for C5 items with the scores for the preferred stages of moral reasoning of the "closest", and, respectively, "close" answers at SRM-SFO

		Stage 1 (closest)	Stage 2 (closest)	Stage 3 (closest)	Stage 4 (closest)	Stage 1 (close)	Stage 2 (close)	Stage 3 (close)	Stage 4 (close)
C5 item 1	ρ coefficient	-.126	.360*	-.232	-.075	-.312*	-.060	-.083	-.200
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.236	.017	.090	.334	.027	.359	.307	.111
	N	35	35	35	35	39	39	39	39
C5 item 2	ρ coefficient	.144	.394**	-.108	-.329*	.207	.258	.120	-.064
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.205	.010	.268	.027	.103	.056	.233	.349
	N	35	35	35	35	39	39	39	39
C5 item 3	ρ coefficient	.148	.498**	.024	-.457**	.074	.123	-.119	-.417**
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.199	.001	.445	.003	.328	.229	.235	.004
	N	35	35	35	35	39	39	39	39

		Stage 1 (closest)	Stage 2 (closest)	Stage 3 (closest)	Stage 4 (closest)	Stage 1 (close)	Stage 2 (close)	Stage 3 (close)	Stage 4 (close)
C5 item 4	p coefficient	.039	.477**	.052	-.450**	.107	.096	-.015	-.242
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.412	.002	.384	.003	.258	.281	.465	.069
	N	35	35	35	35	39	39	39	39
C5 item 5	p coefficient	.042	.348*	-.135	-.257	.086	.243	.104	-.147
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.405	.020	.220	.068	.302	.068	.265	.186
	N	35	35	35	35	39	39	39	39
C5 item 6	p coefficient	.075	.301*	.095	-.354*	.260	.354*	.303*	.169
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.334	.040	.294	.019	.055	.014	.031	.151
	N	35	35	35	35	39	39	39	39
C5 item 7	p coefficient	-.200	.240	.218	-.277	.069	-.021	.168	-.034
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.124	.082	.104	.054	.338	.449	.154	.418
	N	35	35	35	35	39	39	39	39
C5 item 8	p coefficient	.253	.364*	.254	-.548**	-.205	-.097	-.107	-.391**
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.072	.016	.071	.000	.106	.278	.258	.007
	N	35	35	35	35	39	39	39	39
C5 item 9	p coefficient	.171	.300*	.354*	-.457**	-.026	.099	.112	-.253
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.163	.040	.018	.003	.438	.274	.249	.060
	N	35	35	35	35	39	39	39	39
C5 item 10	p coefficient	-.247	-.047	.288*	.057	-.384**	-.157	-.045	-.079
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.076	.393	.047	.373	.008	.171	.393	.317
	N	35	35	35	35	39	39	39	39
C5 item 11	p coefficient	-.083	-.217	-.170	.298*	-.301*	-.335*	-.109	-.294*
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.317	.105	.164	.041	.031	.019	.254	.035
	N	35	35	35	35	39	39	39	39
C5 item 12	p coefficient	-.296*	-.028	.108	.139	-.101	-.053	.012	.047
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.042	.436	.269	.213	.271	.375	.472	.389
	N	35	35	35	35	39	39	39	39
C5 item 13	p coefficient	-.122	-.275	-.010	.257	-.120	-.221	-.136	-.157
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.242	.055	.477	.068	.233	.088	.204	.171
	N	35	35	35	35	39	39	39	39
C5 item 14	p coefficient	-.008	.399**	.229	-.403**	.008	.269*	.287*	-.103
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.482	.009	.092	.008	.480	.049	.038	.266
	N	35	35	35	35	39	39	39	39
C5 item 15	p coefficient	.104	.155	.293*	-.270	.182	.138	.309*	-.161
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.276	.188	.044	.059	.134	.201	.028	.164
	N	35	35	35	35	39	39	39	39
C5 item 16	p coefficient	-.058	.149	-.185	.016	.084	.063	-.109	-.008
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.370	.196	.144	.465	.305	.352	.255	.481
	N	35	35	35	35	39	39	39	39
C5 item 17	p coefficient	.102	.367*	.041	-.361*	.090	.243	.120	-.083
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.279	.015	.408	.016	.293	.068	.233	.308
	N	35	35	35	35	39	39	39	39
C5 item 18	p coefficient	.219	.207	.320*	-.406**	-.113	-.095	-.079	-.351*
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.103	.117	.030	.008	.246	.282	.316	.014
	N	35	35	35	35	39	39	39	39
C5 item 19	p coefficient	.360*	.250	-.040	-.359*	-.097	-.051	-.229	-.322*
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.017	.074	.409	.017	.278	.380	.080	.023
	N	35	35	35	35	39	39	39	39
C5 item 20	p coefficient	.087	.134	-.050	-.096	-.132	.067	-.096	-.071
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.309	.222	.388	.292	.211	.344	.281	.335
	N	35	35	35	35	39	39	39	39
C5 item 21	p coefficient	.085	-.152	-.032	.028	.110	-.012	.026	-.193
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.313	.192	.429	.436	.252	.470	.438	.119
	N	35	35	35	35	39	39	39	39
C5 item 22	p coefficient	-.121	.073	.273	-.198	.050	.142	.224	-.128
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.245	.338	.056	.127	.381	.194	.085	.219
	N	35	35	35	35	39	39	39	39
C5 item 23	p coefficient	.049	.090	.370*	-.362*	.034	.156	.133	.016
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.391	.303	.014	.016	.418	.171	.210	.462
	N	35	35	35	35	39	39	39	39

		Stage 1 (closest)	Stage 2 (closest)	Stage 3 (closest)	Stage 4 (closest)	Stage 1 (close)	Stage 2 (close)	Stage 3 (close)	Stage 4 (close)
C5 item 24	ρ coefficient	-.043	.049	.068	-.023	.113	-.135	-.070	-.171
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.405	.391	.351	.448	.250	.210	.338	.152
	N	34	34	34	34	38	38	38	38
C5 item 25	ρ coefficient	.072	-.058	-.055	.066	-.003	-.063	-.087	-.158
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.343	.372	.378	.355	.492	.354	.303	.172
	N	34	34	34	34	38	38	38	38
C5 item 26	ρ coefficient	-.152	.044	.004	.072	-.188	-.176	-.059	-.195
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.191	.400	.492	.341	.126	.141	.361	.117
	N	35	35	35	35	39	39	39	39
C5 item 27	ρ coefficient	-.070	.143	.114	-.161	.308*	.187	.232	.231
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.347	.210	.260	.181	.028	.127	.078	.079
	N	34	34	34	34	39	39	39	39
C5 item 28	ρ coefficient	-.100	.147	-.010	-.049	.152	.245	.146	.187
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.285	.200	.477	.390	.178	.066	.187	.127
	N	35	35	35	35	39	39	39	39
C5 item 29	ρ coefficient	.070	.488**	.025	-.407**	-.045	.124	.006	-.248
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.345	.001	.444	.008	.392	.225	.486	.064
	N	35	35	35	35	39	39	39	39
C5 item 30	ρ coefficient	.286*	.278	.164	-.342*	-.045	-.021	-.019	-.157
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.048	.053	.173	.022	.392	.449	.454	.170
	N	35	35	35	35	39	39	39	39
C5 item 31	ρ coefficient	.158	.258	.180	-.319*	-.032	-.046	-.204	-.257
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.182	.067	.150	.031	.423	.390	.106	.057
	N	35	35	35	35	39	39	39	39

* $p < .05$ ** $p < .01$